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Investigation of a Charge Insensitive Volume in
XENONnT,
Analysis of Goodness-of-Fit Techniques,
and Feasibility Studies for an Automated Krypton
Assay System

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Abstract

The XENONnT experiment aims to directly detect dark matter (DM) particles using a dual-phase xenon time projection chamber (TPC). A particle interaction is detected via a prompt light signal and a delayed charge signal. In this work, three aspects essential for the direct search for DM are explored.

To contribute to the general characterization of the XENONnT detector, the existence of a volume in the TPC is verified that exhibits a partial or complete loss of the charge signal. This region accounts for about 3 % of the active volume and is largest in the lower outer part of the TPC.

The second part of this work focuses on a systematic study to find suitable goodness-of-fit (GOF) tests for the analysis of typical recoil bands of XENONnT. A strong dependence of the GOF test result on the binning is investigated and a solution using an irregular binning scheme is presented. Compared to several other GOF tests, the tests using this binning are best suited for identifying fits with incomplete models.

In the third part, a contribution is made to the development of a system for the fully automated krypton assay of future DM detectors by providing a proof of concept for an automated gas chromatography system. The system parameter stability of the prototype is demonstrated under realistic conditions with relative errors below 0.15 %.

Zusammenfassung

Das XENONnT Experiment zielt darauf ab, dunkle Materie (DM) Teilchen mit Hilfe einer Zweiphasen-Xenon-Spuredriftkammer (engl. TPC) direkt nachzuweisen. Eine Teilchenwechselwirkung wird über ein promptes Lichtsignal und ein verzögertes Ladungssignal nachgewiesen. In dieser Arbeit werden drei Aspekte untersucht, die für die direkte Suche nach DM notwendig sind.

Zur weiteren Charakterisierung von XENONnT wird die Existenz eines Volumens in der TPC nachgewiesen, welches einen teilweisen oder vollständigen Verlust des Ladungssignals aufweist. Dieser Bereich entspricht etwa 3 % des aktiven Volumens und ist im unteren äußeren Teil der TPC am ausgedehntesten.

Der zweite Teil beschäftigt sich mit einer systematischen Studie zur Ermittlung geeigneter Anpassungstests (engl. GOF-Tests) für die Analyse von Rückstoßbändern in XENONnT. Eine starke Abhängigkeit des Testergebnisses von der Partitionierung wird untersucht und zur Lösung dieses Problems wird ein Algorithmus zur unregelmäßigen Partitionierung vorgestellt. Im Vergleich zu verschiedenen anderen GOF-Tests sind die so partitionierten Tests am besten geeignet, um Anpassungen mit unvollständigen Modellen zu identifizieren.

Als Drittes wird die Entwicklung eines automatisierten Gaschromatographiesystems beschrieben, um dessen Realisierbarkeit für ein System für die vollautomatische Krypton-Bestimmung zukünftiger DM Detektoren zu zeigen. Die Stabilität der Systemparameter des Prototypen wird unter realistischen Bedingungen gezeigt mit relativen Fehlern unter 0.15 %.

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1 Introduction: The Search for Dark Matter

Numerous observations on astronomical and cosmological scales provide evidence for gravitational interactions of baryonic matter with non-luminous (“dark”) matter. In the following, a brief introduction to the evidence for dark matter (DM) and approaches for direct DM searches is given. A comprehensive overview can be found in [1], [2]. An early hint for dark matter (DM) on galactic scales was provided by Fritz Zwicky in 1933, who studied the dispersion velocities of galaxies in the Coma cluster [3]. Using the virial theorem, he concluded that the mass of the cluster would need to be much larger than observed from the luminous matter to explain the unexpectedly high velocities. Vera Rubin and collaborators later examined the rotational velocities of stars in spiral galaxies [4]. They observed that the rotational velocities are approximately constant for large distances r from the galactic center. From Newtonian dynamics, however, one would expect a decrease of radial velocities proportional to $r^{-1/2}$ in the outer region of galaxies. Both observations in galaxy clusters and individual galaxies could be explained by the existence of halos of uniformly distributed DM around most galaxies.

The cosmic microwave background (CMB) can be used to determine important cosmological parameters with high precision. Its anisotropies encode information about the density variations in the early universe when the photons were emitted. Precise measurements of the CMB, as performed by the Planck collaboration [5], allow extracting information about the energy content of our universe. From these measurements, one can infer that the mass-energy density of DM is five times as large as the one of baryonic matter [6]. Furthermore, compelling evidence for the existence of DM comes from observations employing gravitational lensing effects, in which the gravitational influence of DM on luminous matter can be directly probed [7]. In addition, it was shown that for the large-structure formation observed in our universe, the existence of non-baryonic DM is an essential building block [8], [9].

The indirect evidence for the existence of DM via its gravitational interaction with baryonic matter is overwhelming. A common way to explain the otherwise puzzling observations is to introduce one or more new elementary particles beyond the standard model of particle physics. Plenty theories predict the existence of such particles that comply with certain constraints imposed by observations [1]. This includes that the hypothetical particles must be *massive* to explain the gravitational phenomena, *dark* in a sense that they do not (or only very feebly) couple to the electromagnetic force, and *non-relativistic* at the time when galaxies started forming. Moreover, they would need to be *stable* to have not decayed until now. However, so far, none of the proposed particle DM candidates were directly detected.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the "WIMP wind" caused by the revolution of the Sun around the galactic centre. The additional revolution of the Earth around the Sun would cause an annual modulation of the relative velocity and thus of the expected interaction rate. From [34].

A generic class of particle DM candidates with typical masses between GeV/c^2 and a few TeV/c^2 is referred to as weakly interacting massive particles (WIMPs), which arise in various theories [10], [11]. The idea to directly detect WIMPs in underground detectors was proposed by Goodman and Witten [12] in 1985. Various experiments have been developed to pursue such measurements [13], [14]. On its orbit around the galactic center, the Solar System moves towards the Cygnus constellation with a velocity of about 220 km/s. This causes the Earth to move with a relative velocity to the predicted DM halo, giving rise to a "WIMP wind" blowing from the direction of the Cygnus constellation, as illustrated in fig. 1.1. A suitable detector could observe the recoil energy of a target nucleus that is hit by such a WIMP. Targets used for direct detection include liquid noble gases [15]–[20], solid state crystals [21]–[32], and superheated fluids [33]. A recoil induced by a WIMP can be observed through the detection of heat (phonons in the case of crystals), charge from ionization of the target material or – in case of a scintillating detector – light from the de-excitation of the scintillating target material. While detecting one of these signals is sufficient to infer the nuclear recoil energy, the simultaneous measurement of two signals can be used for background discrimination, as it is the case for XENONnT discussed in chapter 2. A selection of direct WIMP experiments, grouped according to their detection channel(s), is shown in fig. 1.2.

In chapter 2, the setup and working principle of the XENONnT DM detector is summarized. Special emphasis is given on the calibration of the detector and

Figure 1.2: Selection of different direct WIMP experiments grouped by their detection channel(s).

important sources of background. The sensitivity required for the search for DM places high demands on a variety of tasks. Three different aspects are studied in this thesis. An investigation of a region insensitive to the charge signal of a particle interactions in XENONnT is presented in chapter 3. Chapter 4 features different studies on the performance of various goodness-of-fit tests for identifying fits with incomplete models in XENONnT. It is followed by the description of a prototype for an automated gas chromatography system to separate krypton and xenon in chapter 5. This is a first step towards a fully automated system for the krypton assay in xenon for future DM detectors.

2 The XENONnT Dark Matter Experiment

The XENONnT experiment primarily aims to directly detect dark matter using a noble-gas dual-phase time projection chamber (TPC). In the past, the XENON collaboration operated various TPCs with instrumented liquid xenon (LXe) targets of 14 kg (XENON10 [35]), 62 kg (XENON100 [36]), and 2.0 t (XENON1T [37]). The current stage of the experiment, XENONnT, features a TPC with an active target of 5.9 t and is operated at the underground laboratory of the INFN Laboratori Nazionali del Gran Sasso in Italy. With an exposure of 20 t yr, XENONnT will be sensitive to a spin-independent WIMP-nucleon cross-section that is more than one order of magnitude smaller than the current best limit in a blinded analysis achieved by XENON1T [15], [38]. Another major science goal of XENONnT is to probe the excess of electronic recoil events observed in XENON1T [39].

Besides XENONnT, two more multi-ton dual-phase xenon TPCs are currently being operated for direct dark matter searches: LUX-ZEPLIN (LZ) [16] and PandaX-4T [17], [40]. A future dark matter detector featuring a TPC filled with 40 t of LXe, requiring a total mass of about 50 t of LXe, was proposed by the DARWIN collaboration [41]. This massive detector would have unprecedented sensitivity to spin-independent WIMP scattering, probing the remaining parameter space down to the regime where background from neutrinos becomes dominant. Moreover, such a detector could have a rich science program with competitive sensitivity to various other particle dark matter candidates and neutrinoless double-beta decay. At the same time, it would serve as an observatory for a variety of interesting astrophysical neutrinos [42].

In this chapter, the setup and working principle of XENONnT are described. Then, the calibration of the detector is discussed, and an overview of the steps towards reconstructing an event from a particle interaction is given. Finally, relevant background sources and the means of their mitigation are summarized.

2.1 The Subsystems of XENONnT

XENONnT comprises three nested detectors. The TPC inside a double-walled cryostat is surrounded by an active neutron veto (NV), which in turn is enclosed by an active muon veto (MV), which is contained in a cylindrical stainless steel tank. A schematic drawing of the setup is shown in fig. 2.1. The working principle of a LXe dual-phase TPC in general, and of the XENONnT TPC in particular, are discussed in section 2.2. The active NV is filled with Gd-loaded water and instrumented with

120 photomultiplier tubes (PMTs). Neutrons that propagate through the water tank are moderated and eventually captured by Gd or H. In both cases, one or more secondary γ -rays are produced. Part of the energy of the γ -rays is transferred to electrons by Compton scattering. The Cherenkov photons radiated by the electrons are then detected by the PMTs. This allows tagging events in the TPC that coincide with the exit of a neutron. The active MV hosts about 700 t of Gd-loaded water. It is contained by a cylindrical stainless steel tank and optically separated from the NV by highly reflective expanded polytetrafluoroethylene (ePTFE) panels. The volume is instrumented with 84 PMTs to operate as an active Cherenkov muon veto [43]. At the same time, the water acts as a passive shield against external γ - and neutron radiation. The Gd-loading is not relevant for the operation of the MV and is merely a consequence of the fact that NV and MV are only optically separated by the ePTFE panels.

The three detectors are connected to several auxiliary subsystems, that are accommodated in a three-story service building next to the water tank. Systems for the purification of LXe and gaseous xenon (GXe) are operated to achieve and maintain a concentration of electronegative impurities, most importantly O_2 , below 1 ppb¹. This is important because such impurities deteriorate the observed charge signal. For this purpose, hot-getters and copper filters are employed. Two dedicated cryogenic distillation columns are installed to remove ^{85}Kr [44], [45] and ^{222}Rn [46], [47], which are the two largest intrinsic background sources in the xenon target. Both columns exploit the different vapor pressures of the contaminant and xenon. Moreover, the service building houses the cryogenic system of the cryostat, systems for the recovery and storage of LXe (ReStoX-I and ReStoX-II in front of the building), data acquisition (DAQ), and slow control.

¹ppm = 10^{-6} , ppb = 10^{-9} , ppt = 10^{-12} , ppq = 10^{-15}

Figure 2.1: Schematic drawing of the XENONnT setup. The time projection chamber (TPC) is placed inside a water tank, which also contains an active neutron veto (n veto) and muon veto. The detectors are connected to numerous auxiliary systems in a three-story building. More details on all subsystems are provided in the text. From [48].

2.2 Dual-Phase Xenon Time Projection Chamber

Liquid xenon exhibits a variety of properties, which make it well suited as a target material for various low background searches. The high nuclear charge of $Z = 54$ in combination with a density of about 2.9 g/cm^3 results in a large stopping power for charged particles. This efficiently reduces the rate of external radiation in the inner part of a LXe volume (xenon self-shielding). Moreover, xenon does not contain any long-lived radioactive isotopes, which reduces internal backgrounds. When a particle interacts with xenon, the medium is ionized and scintillation photons are emitted. These two signals can be used for position reconstruction of the interaction and background discrimination.

2.2.1 General Operating Principle

The advantageous properties of LXe are exploited in a two-phase xenon TPC, the operating principle of which is illustrated in fig. 2.2. The detector consists of a LXe target and a volume of GXe used for signal amplification. If a particle interacts with the target material, excited xenon dimers Xe_2^* (excimers) as well as electron-ion pairs are produced. Part of the energy is also deposited in the form of thermal energy, but the detector is not sensitive to this signal. On a timescale of $\mathcal{O}(10 \text{ ns})$, the Xe_2^* excimers decay by emitting vacuum-ultraviolet (VUV) scintillation photons with a most probable wavelength of $\lambda = 175 \text{ nm}$ [49]. This prompt scintillation signal is referred to as $S1$ signal. The target is essentially transparent to its own scintillation light since the energy levels of single xenon atoms differ from those of xenon dimers. The signal from the freed charges is extracted by drifting the electrons to the liquid-gas interface with an electric field E_{drift} applied across the target between the cathode

Figure 2.2: Working principle of a dual-phase time projection chamber (TPC). A particle interaction with the target produces a prompt scintillation signal $S1$ and a delayed and amplified ionization signal $S2$ from drifted electrons. Both signals are detected by suitable photosensor arrays at the top and bottom of the cylindrical detector. The depth of the interaction is inferred from the drift time of the electrons and the radial position is obtained from the distribution of the $S2$ signal in the top photosensor array. Image credit: Lutz Althüser.

and gate electrode. A second electric field $E_{\text{extraction}} > E_{\text{drift}}$ is applied across the liquid-gas interface between gate and anode to extract and accelerate the charges into the GXe volume. The energy provided by the second field suffices to excite and ionize the gas atoms. This results in a secondary VUV scintillation light signal $S2$, which is proportional to the number of extracted electrons [50]. The scintillation light from the $S1$ and $S2$ signals is detected with suitable photon detectors at the top and bottom of the cylindrical volume, which convert light quanta into charge. The signals are measured in units of PE, which corresponds to the average measured charge created in a sensor when a single photoelectron is generated. $S2$ signals can be distinguished from $S1$ signals based on their longer duration of $\mathcal{O}(10 \mu\text{s})$ as a consequence of longitudinal diffusion of the electrons along their path through the target and their different pulse shapes. Part of the initially separated charges recombine, forming more excimers. Thus, for constant deposited energy, $S1$ and $S2$ signals are anti-correlated. By reconstructing the energy from both signals, a higher energy resolution can be obtained [51].

Combining the information of both signals also allows to reconstruct the three-dimensional position of the particle interaction in the target volume. The depth

z is extracted from the drift time of the electrons, which corresponds to the time difference between the S1 signal and the S2 signal. The radial position (r, θ) is inferred from the hit pattern of the S2 signal in the photosensors. This enables to select an inner *fiducial volume* (FV) with low contamination from external radiation due to the strong self-shielding of LXe.

Moreover, the ratio of both signals can be used to determine the type of particle interaction. One can distinguish between electronic recoils (ERs), where a particle scatters off a xenon shell electron, and nuclear recoils (NRs), where a particle recoils off the entire nucleus. ERs show on average larger S2/S1 ratios compared to NRs, as can be seen in fig. 2.3. The scintillation response of LXe to ER and NR is successfully modeled by the quasi-empirical Noble Element Simulation Technique (NEST) [52], [53]. Accordingly, a probability for the type of interaction can be derived from the position of an event in the S1-S2 plane, which can be used to statistically mitigate ER background. In XENON1T, an ER rejection of 99.7% with about 50% NR acceptance was achieved [38].

2.2.2 The XENONnT Time Projection Chamber

XENONnT employs a cylindrical dual-phase TPC with an active target mass of 5.9 t LXe. The active region of the TPC is the cylindrical volume between the gate electrode and the cathode with a height of about 149 cm and an inner radius of about 66 cm. The VUV photons of S1 and S2 signals are detected by two arrays of PMTs at the top and the bottom of the detector. In total, 494 3-inch PMTs² [55], [56] are used, 253 in the top and 241 in the bottom array. The TPC wall is formed by 24 polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) panels, which are connected in a light-tight manner by 24 vertical PTFE pillars. They are specially treated with diamond tools to maximize their reflectivity of VUV light [57]. The electric fields for the electron drift and extraction are generated by the anode, gate, and cathode electrodes, each of which is made of stainless steel wires housed in a stainless steel frame. To increase the uniformity of the drift field inside the active volume, field-shaping wires connected by a resistor chain, as well as copper guard rings, are used. In addition, two screening electrodes are installed below (above) the top (bottom) PMT array to shield the PMTs from strong electric fields. The level of the liquid-gas interface in the TPC is maintained with a pressurized stainless steel “diving bell”. A right-handed cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) is defined with origin at the center of the gate electrode such that the cathode is at $z = -149$ cm. For many applications, a cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z) with radius from the central axis of the TPC r and azimuth angle θ is used. The TPC is located inside a double-walled cryostat which hosts the full 8.4 t LXe inventory.

²Hamamatsu R11410-21

Figure 2.3: Calibration measurements performed with a ^{220}Rn source producing electronic recoils (ERs, top) and with a neutron generator resulting in nuclear recoils (NRs, bottom). The medians of the distributions are shown in blue (ER) and red (NR) in both plots, which illustrates the discrimination ability. The c in front of the parameters indicates that the signals are corrected and the subscript b denotes that only the signal in the bottom PMT array is considered. From [54].

Figure 2.4: Rendering of the XENONnT time projection chamber (TPC) inside the double-walled cryostat. On the right side, two regions of the TPC are magnified, showing the grid regions and the field shaping elements. Credit: Jacques Pienaar.

2.3 XENONnT Calibration

Calibration measurements are essential to characterize the response of the detector and monitor its stability over time. Three important calibration campaigns of XENONnT are discussed in the following.

Krypton Calibration: The meta-stable isotope ^{83m}Kr is a common calibration source used in LXe detectors [58]–[60]. The strong self-shielding of LXe is one of the major selling points of this material as a target for low background searches. However, this also makes it impossible to calibrate the inner part of the volume with low-energy ERs with an external source. As an alternative, one can directly dissolve a calibration source in the target material, as it is done for ^{83m}Kr . The isotope decays with a half-life of 1.83 h to the stable ground state ^{83}Kr , which is important for quickly recovering low-background conditions after a calibration. The decay happens in two steps, mainly by emitting two conversion electrons with energies of 32.1 keV and 9.4 keV. The short half-life between the two transitions of 154 ns allows to tag events with this characteristic signature. The uniformly distributed krypton calibration data is used for various calibrations and corrections, as described in section 2.4. During continuous science data taking, a krypton calibration measurement is performed every two weeks. For this purpose, a ^{83}Rb source is stored in the purification system, which decays to ^{83m}Kr with a half-life of 86.2 days. When required, the produced ^{83m}Kr then can be injected into the detector by flushing the source with GXe from the purification loop.

Radon Calibration: Similar to the krypton calibration, ^{220}Rn is dissolved in the LXe target for calibration measurements. A source containing ^{220}Rn -emanating ^{228}Th is flushed with GXe to transport the emanated ^{220}Rn into the TPC [61], [62]. In the

Table 2.1: Three positions of the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source used to calibrate the detector. The position of the source in z , θ , and the radial distance to the outer edge of the active volume Δr are given. In addition, the acquisition time for each position during the first science run is provided.

Position Name	z [cm]	θ [rad]	Δr [cm]	Acquisition Time [h]
<i>top</i>	-10.2	-1.56	30.0	11.0
<i>bottom 1</i>	-91.0	-0.36	41.1	10.0
<i>bottom 2</i>	-95.6	-1.43	41.6	25.2

decay chain of ^{220}Rn , α -, β -, and γ -radiation is produced, which can all be used for calibration. The β -decay of ^{212}Pb with a Q-value of 570 keV produces low-energy single-scatter ERs, which are used to fit the low-energy ER band model as shown in fig. 2.3. With 10.6 h, ^{212}Pb has the longest half-life of the ^{220}Rn decay chain. Thus, after one week, the activity is already reduced by a factor $\sim 6 \times 10^4$, which makes it suitable as an internal calibration source.

AmBe Calibration: The external $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source consists of α -decaying ^{241}Am and ^9Be . In an (α, n) -process on beryllium, a neutron is emitted with an average neutron energy of 4.2 MeV:

The process leaves the carbon atom in an excited nuclear state $^{12}\text{C}^*$, which decays by emitting a 4.4 MeV γ -ray. For a calibration measurement, the isotropic $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source is placed in the vicinity of the TPC inside one of two u-shaped tubes through the water tank that encircle the cryostat. As shown in fig. 2.5, the two tubes are located at different positions in z . Calibration data is acquired with different positions of the source. The three positions with sufficiently high statistics in the TPC are summarized in table 2.1. In addition, measurements in which the source was far away from the TPC were performed to calibrate the active NV.

Radiative capture of thermal neutrons on hydrogen in water gives rise to a 2.22 MeV γ -ray, which corresponds to the binding energy of deuterium. In the TPC, neutrons from the source can activate xenon nuclei. The activated nuclei ^{129}Xe and ^{131}Xe decay after about 1 ns by emitting a γ -ray of 39.58 keV and 80.19 keV, respectively [63]. The metastable nuclei ^{129m}Xe and ^{131m}Xe have half-lives of about 10 d, which is sufficient to homogeneously distribute in the TPC. They decay by emitting a γ -ray of 236.14 keV and 163.93 keV, respectively [63]. The low energetic neutrons are used to calibrate the detector response to NRs. The various mono-energetic γ -rays induced by the calibration measurement are used to calibrate the energy scale of the detector as described in section 2.3.

Figure 2.5: Location of the two u-tubes that encircle the cryostat. A three-dimensional histogram of calibration data is shown. The indicated source positions correspond to *top* (left) and *bottom 2* (right) from table 2.1. Credit: Jacques Pienaar.

2.4 Event Reconstruction

A series of steps must be performed to reconstruct an event with a three-dimensional position and energy from the prompt scintillation and charge signals detected by the 494 PMTs. The following is a brief overview of the machinery in place for event reconstruction in XENONnT.

2.4.1 Event Identification

The signals detected by the PMTs are amplified and read out by the triggerless XENONnT DAQ system. The data is processed with the data framework *strax* [64] and the XENONnT specific analysis framework *straxen* [65]. Raw data signals above a predefined threshold are classified as hits. The hits of all channels are summed and clustered in disjoint time windows of peak candidates. Those candidates are classified and, if applicable, merged to obtain S1 and S2 peaks. Sufficiently large peaks indicate an event, which usually contains an S1 and an S2 peak. If multiple S1 and S2 peaks are combined into one event, the largest S1 and largest S2 are classified as the main peaks of the event. The second-largest S1 in an event is classified as an alternative S1 (AS1) signal. The largest S2 peak other than the main S2, which occurs in a time interval after the main S1 signal, is classified as an alternative S2 signal (AS2) of the event.

2.4.2 Position Reconstruction

In XENONnT, three deep learning algorithms are implemented to reconstruct the position of an event in (x, y) based on the S2 hit-pattern on the top PMT array. All

three algorithms are trained with simulated data. With the same technique, in the inner part of the XENON1T TPC, a radial position resolution of about 1.9 cm for $S2 = 200$ PE and below 0.8 cm for larger charge signals was achieved. For larger radii, the resolution was a factor ~ 1.5 worse due to non-functional PMTs and geometrical effects [54]. Similar resolutions are expected in XENONnT.

The depth of an interaction is obtained from the drift time t_{drift} , which corresponds to the difference between the average S2 time and the average S1 time. The product of the drift time and the constant drift velocity v_d yields the z position of the interaction. The latter can be determined empirically using ^{83m}Kr data via the maximal observed drift time and the known cathode-gate distance. The maximal observed drift time needs to be corrected for the small additional drift time in the liquid phase above the gate.

Slight distortions of the drift field cause an inwards bias of events increasing with z as well as a structure in θ . This reconstruction bias is corrected based on the distribution of ^{83m}Kr events in (x, y, z) . For the correction, one uses the fact that electric field lines never cross and hence the percentiles of the radial distribution are conserved. The observed radii of ^{83m}Kr events are remapped in slices of z and θ such that the expected uniform radial distribution with a maximum radius corresponding to the TPC radius is achieved [54]. This correction of the reconstructed position is referred to as *field distortion correction*.

2.4.3 Signal Corrections

The observed signal sizes of S1 and S2 are position-dependent due to various non-symmetric detector effects. The observed signals are corrected for the detector response at the reconstructed interaction position to obtain corrected values cS1 and cS2 with a spatially uniform response. This way, one can omit including the position-dependent response in the detector model. All corrections are based on the corrected position (x, y, z) of an event. Therefore, a precise position reconstruction is an important prerequisite for the following corrections.

The observed S1 size for a given deposited energy depends on the position of the interaction due to geometrical effects such as the position-dependent solid angle that is directly covered with PMTs. A data-driven light collection efficiency (LCE) map in (x, y, z) is used to correct this position dependence. Events of the mono-energetic combined 41.6 keV line of ^{83m}Kr are selected and the average size of S1 is obtained for bins in (r, θ, z) . The relative light yield is defined as the ratio of the binwise average size of S1 and the average of all bins. It is maximal above the center of the bottom PMT array and minimal in the upper outer region of the TPC. A continuous map is generated by interpolation. Each S1 is then divided by the relative light yield at the interaction point (x, y, z) to obtain cS1. The simulated LCE map of XENONnT is shown in fig. 2.6 (left).

Electronegative impurities in LXe, such as O_2 , can temporarily bind ionization electrons. If the impurities are uniformly distributed in the TPC, the number of electrons that arrive at the gate is given by $N_e = N_{e,0} e^{-t_{\text{drift}}/\tau_e}$. Here, $N_{e,0}$ is the

Figure 2.6: Left: Simulated map of the light collection efficiency (LCE) for XENONnT. The projection in radius R and z are shown in the bottom and right panels respectively. The location of the electrodes are indicated by dotted red lines. **Right:** Simulated fraction of the S2 light detected by the bottom PMT array. The diagonal structures are due to wires, which are stretched perpendicular to the electrode wires of anode and gate to prevent sagging. From [15].

initial number of ionization electrons, t_{drift} is the drift time of the electron cloud and τ_e is the so-called *electron lifetime*, which corresponds to the average time for an electron to propagate through the drift volume until it is trapped by an electronegative impurity. This effect gives rise to a z -dependent S2 signal. To correct for this effect, the observed S2 size is divided by the expected deterioration of the charge signal based on the observed depth of the interaction z . The target material is continuously purified, which makes τ_e time dependent. Therefore, the evolution of τ_e is constantly monitored during operation. This is accomplished by mapping the charge signal of mono-energetic events as a function of the drift time. The α -decays of the internal backgrounds ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po are used for an estimation on a daily basis. Additionally, the combined 41.5 keV signal of the two consecutive decays of ^{83m}Kr are used to determine τ_e with higher accuracy during the biweekly krypton-calibration.

Furthermore, the S2 signal varies in (x, y) due to non-uniform charge collection. This can be caused by varying gas gain and extraction efficiency due to variations in the extraction field caused by wire sagging, as well as turned-off PMTs. To account for this position dependence, a map similar to the S1 correction map in (x, y) is constructed using the combined ^{83m}Kr line. The simulated (x, y) -dependence of the S2 signal is illustrated in fig. 2.6 (right).

2.4.4 Electronic-Recoil Combined Energy Scale

To reconstruct the energy deposited in the TPC by ERs, the anti-correlated charge and light signals of an event are combined. Nearly the entire deposited energy of ERs is converted into n_{ph} scintillation photons and n_e electron-ion pairs. With the mean energy required to produce a photon or electron-ion-pair $W = 13.7 \text{ eV}$, the total deposited energy can thus be written as

$$E = W(n_{\text{ph}} + n_e) = W \left(\frac{cS1}{g_1} + \frac{cS2}{g_2} \right). \quad (2.2)$$

The average primary scintillation gain $g_1 = cS1/n_{\text{ph}}$ and the average secondary scintillation gain $g_2 = cS2/n_e$ are detector specific constants. They are determined by a fit to the cS1 and cS2 values of the numerous mono-energetic lines in calibration data [36], [37], [66].

2.5 Backgrounds and Background Mitigation in XENONnT

In order to be sensitive to a signal from dark matter, it is crucial to achieve an ultra-low background level in the detector. External background mainly originates from γ -radiation, neutrons, and neutrinos. In addition, internal backgrounds that are either intrinsic or arise from construction materials in contact with the target material play an important role. β - and γ -radiation predominantly interact electromagnetically with atomic electrons, which cause ER background. Neutrons on the other hand mainly scatter off the atomic nucleus, causing NR background. Neutrinos contribute to both NR and ER background. The expected signal in the detector from a WIMP is a single NR. Therefore, neutrons and neutrinos, which can produce the same single scatter NR signal, are critical backgrounds for direct dark matter searches. As mentioned in section 2.2, ER backgrounds can efficiently be distinguished from NR signals based on their larger S2/S1 ratio. However, statistical leakage of the ER population gives rise to ERs that are indistinguishable from the signal of a WIMP.

In addition to physical interactions, accidental coincidence (AC) events are an important source of background. Those signals can occur if either the S1 or S2 of an interaction is lost in the non-active region of the TPC. The lone S1 and S2 signals can mimic a physical interaction if they are reconstructed with a compatible time difference.

As noted in section 2.2, selecting an inner FV for the analysis effectively suppresses various backgrounds due to the strong self-shielding of LXe. The design FV for XENONnT is a cylindrical volume with a LXe mass of 4t that has a distance of approximately 6 cm to the TPC wall. The exact bounds of the FV are defined based on data-driven background models to maximize the sensitivity of the experiment.

In the following, a selection of background sources is presented and the strategies to reject these backgrounds in XENONnT are motivated.

Figure 2.7: Expected energy spectra of the electronic recoil (ER, left) and nuclear recoil (NR, right) backgrounds in XENONnT in a 4t fiducial volume. The WIMP search energy region of interest is indicated in white. The ER rates do not account for the reduction due to the discrimination of NR and ER in the S1-S2 space. From [15]

2.5.1 Nuclear Recoil Background

Nuclear recoil background arises from neutrons and neutrinos that produce a single scatter in the TPC. These events are indistinguishable from the expected WIMP signal on an event-by-event basis and thus require special attention.

Radiogenic neutrons of a few MeV energy can be produced by (α, n) - and spontaneous fission reactions in the detector materials and can penetrate several centimeters into the active volume. The radiogenic neutron rate in the energy region of interest (ROI) is expected to be reduced by approximately an order of magnitude due to the active neutron veto [15]. Cosmogenic neutrons are produced when fast atmospheric muons interact with the rock surrounding the experiment. These neutrons have energies up to several GeV but they can lose energy by moderation, resulting in neutrons with energies in the signal region. A suppression of cosmogenic neutrons to a negligible level has already been achieved in XENON1T via the active muon veto [43].

Solar, atmospheric and diffuse supernova (DSN) neutrinos can produce NRs through coherent elastic neutrino-nucleus scattering ($\text{CE}\nu\text{NS}$). As it is not possible to shield an experiment from neutrinos, those interactions eventually limit the sensitivity of the classical approaches for direct WIMP detection. The cross-section at which $\text{CE}\nu\text{NS}$ becomes the dominant background of an experiment is often referred to as the *neutrino floor* [67]. However, the term *neutrino fog* [68] is probably more appropriate since even beyond this level, direct dark matter searches are possible with sufficient statistics.

2.5.2 Electronic Recoil Background

Detector Material: Gamma radiation from radioactive contamination of the construction material can penetrate up to a few centimeters into the active volume. Single low-energy Compton electrons can then give rise to ER background in the signal region. Fiducialization effectively suppresses this background due to the high self-shielding power of LXe. To reduce the γ -radiation from materials to begin with, only materials with high radiopurity are used to build XENONnT. For this, the radioactive contamination of all materials is screened in a dedicated radioassay campaign [69]. The measurements allow selecting materials with a high radiopurity and also serve as an input for Monte Carlo simulations of the expected background levels. The expected energy spectrum of ERs from materials is shown in purple in fig. 2.7 (left). The main contributions to this background in XENONnT come from the PMTs (51 %) and the two cryostat vessels (41 %) [15].

Radon: Small traces of the primordial isotope ^{238}U in the material give rise to the constant production of ^{222}Rn , which can emanate into the active volume. Due to its half-life of 3.8 d, ^{222}Rn can distribute homogeneously in the TPC before it decays further. Therefore, the decays from ^{222}Rn pose a source of background that cannot be mitigated by fiducialization. The most critical daughter isotope for dark matter searches is the β -decaying ^{214}Pb , which can produce ERs in the signal ROI. In XENONnT, a lower radon level compared to XENON1T is expected due to the smaller surface-area-to-volume ratio of the TPC. In addition, cryogenic radon distillation is used during data-taking to reduce the concentration of ^{222}Rn further [46], [47]. Still, the progeny of ^{222}Rn is expected to be the dominant ER background in XENONnT in the WIMP ROI, as one can see in fig. 2.7 (orange line, left).

Krypton: Commercially available xenon is extracted from air, which naturally contains krypton $^{\text{nat}}\text{Kr}$ at the ppm to ppb level. This includes traces of the anthropogenic isotope ^{85}Kr released into the air by nuclear fuel reprocessing plants and nuclear weapons. The relative isotope abundance $^{85}\text{Kr} / ^{\text{nat}}\text{Kr}$ was determined to be about 2×10^{-11} mol/mol [70]. The radioactive ^{85}Kr is an almost pure β^- emitter, decaying with a half-life of 10.76 yr and a Q-value of $Q_\beta = 678$ keV. The resulting β -spectrum induces ERs in the energy ROI. Similar to ^{222}Rn , the ERs induced by ^{85}Kr cannot be reduced by fiducialization since krypton is homogeneously distributed in the active volume. In XENON1T, the concentration of $^{\text{nat}}\text{Kr}$ in xenon was reduced by almost five orders of magnitude to (360 ± 60) ppq by cryogenic krypton distillation [46]. Even though the expected rate of ^{85}Kr decays is about a factor five lower than that expected from ^{222}Rn progeny (fig. 2.7 left, red line), it is crucial to determine the exact level of ^{85}Kr in the detector for a robust data analysis. Therefore, the krypton concentration in xenon is regularly measured during data-taking. For this, a xenon sample from the active volume is extracted and the amount of krypton is measured, as detailed in section 5.1.

2.5.3 Surface Background

During the detector construction, the inner PTFE surfaces are exposed to ambient air, which contains progeny of ^{222}Rn . Those radioactive isotopes can contaminate the inner detector surface by plating out. The decays of ^{210}Pb with a half-life of 22.3 y and its daughters give rise to a constant source of background from the inner detector surface during data acquisition. The β - and γ -radiation of ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Bi can create ERs in the detector, which can lose part of the charge to the wall. These ER events with reduced S2 signal can have an S1/S2 ratio compatible with NRs. Due to larger position reconstruction uncertainties at low S2, such events can leak into the FV [54]. Additionally, NR background can arise from the decay of ^{210}Po via its daughter nucleus ^{206}Pb and emitted neutrons from (α, n) -reactions.

To mitigate this background contribution, a dedicated surface treatment of the PTFE walls was performed prior to the start of the experiment [71].

3 Verification and Characterization of a Charge Insensitive Volume in XENONnT

From field simulations performed by a member of the collaboration [72] with the field configuration of XENONnT during science run 0 (SR0), a region of charge loss is expected in the outer part of the TPC. Such a region arises due to field lines that end at the wall of the TPC instead of at the top.

3.1 The Charge Insensitive Volume and Partial Charge Loss Volume

If an electron follows a field line that ends at the wall, it is not extracted into the gas phase and thus does not produce a charge signal. In the extreme case, this leads to a complete loss of the charge signal of an interaction, corresponding to a *charge insensitive volume* (CIV) in the detector. Depending on the interaction point, part of the charges may be recovered due to diffusion of electrons along their drift path. This gives rise to an associated *partial charge loss volume* (PCLV), in which only a fraction of the full charge signal is lost, causing smaller observed charge signals $cS2_{\text{observed}}$. The boundary between the two volumes is defined as the area at which the $cS2_{\text{observed}}$ falls below the detection threshold of about 200 PE for SR0. A simplified diagram, which shows the location of a PCLV between the regions of field lines that end at the top of the TPC and field lines that end at the wall is shown in fig. 3.1. As shown in the diagram, due to diffusion, partial charge loss can also occur for events with interaction points on field lines that end at the top. The maximal average charge loss in this region is 50% at the boundary to the region with field lines that end at the wall. In the following, only the volume with a charge loss larger than 50% is considered as PCLV. The combined volume of CIV and PCLV is referred to as *charge loss volume*. The remaining volume is referred to as the *charge sensitive volume* (CSV).

The size and location of the CIV and PCLV depend on the potentials of the field-shaping elements, which are chosen to maximize the field homogeneity in the inner part of the TPC while keeping the size of the charge loss volume reasonably low. The total mass with charge loss above 50% expected from simulations is about 120 kg. The fraction of the mass with complete loss of the charge (CIV) is by definition 100% for $\langle cS2_{\text{full}} \rangle = 200$ PE and less than 50% for $\langle cS2_{\text{full}} \rangle = 10^6$ PE. The latter corresponds to the expected charge signal of high energy γ -rays. For a quantitative description

Figure 3.1: Schematic illustration of the regions with different charge signals in the TPC. Most field lines end at the anode at the top of the TPC (blue region). Charges following these field lines are amplified in the gas phase (charge sensitive volume). If in turn charges follow a field line that ends at the wall (red), they cannot be detected (charge insensitive volume). Near the boundary between the two volumes, charges can diffuse from one volume to the other, creating the partial charge loss volume (hashed).

of the charge loss volume, the *charge survival fraction* (CSF) is introduced, which corresponds to the average fraction of charges that reach the amplification region for a given position in the TPC. This distribution can be obtained by simulating the propagation of electrons based on the field simulation for fixed positions in the TPC. A map for the entire TPC is then created by interpolation. In XENON1T, an accumulation of negative charges at the PTFE panels was observed. This was attributed to the fact that the field-shaping elements were not in contact with the panels [54]. To improve this, in XENONnT, the wires were directly contacted with the PTFE panels and 360 charge-collecting holes with a diameter of 0.25 mm were regularly distributed on each panel. As a consequence, data now suggest a more efficient removal of negative charges from the panels compared to the pillars, giving rise to a higher charge density on the pillars. This gives rise to different CSF profiles expected for the two regions as shown in fig. 3.2.

If a charge loss volume is present in the TPC, it can have several implications for data analysis. If the CIV is much larger than expected from field simulations, it would result in a substantial loss of exposure, which is a key factor in the planning and scheduling of the experiment’s scientific program. Moreover, any CIV will result in a certain bias of the position of an event due to an incorrect field distortion correction. As discussed in section 2.4.2, the reconstructed positions of the events are remapped to become radially uniformly distributed, with the maximum radius being equal to the edge of the TPC. If, however, a CIV is present, events that occur at the radius of the boundary between PCLV and CIV are mapped to the TPC edge.

Figure 3.2: Expected charge survival fraction at the PTFE pillars and panels from field simulations. The different maps are a result of a different charge-up behavior of the two regions. The apparent line structure aligns with the location of the field shaping wires of the TPC.

Events from further inside the TPC are scaled accordingly so that, also here, a slight mismatch between true and reconstructed position is introduced by the correction. Events from the PCLV give rise to surface background. This background source is modeled in a dedicated analysis. However, an understanding of the causative PCLV and, in particular, the dependence of its size on the S2 size can help to improve this model. Furthermore, especially for calibration campaigns with external sources, a considerable fraction of events could suffer from partial charge loss. If not taken into account, the calibration would be biased.

Therefore, it is important to investigate the location and extent of a potential charge loss volume in the TPC by using data. After verifying whether such a volume exists, the most critical information is whether or not one can exclude that it is much larger than expected from the field simulation. To answer these questions and to further characterize the charge loss volume, several data-driven studies were conducted. For a comprehensive analysis, events from all three regions – the CSV, PCLV, and the CIV – have to be examined. The standard position reconstruction algorithm based on information of the S2 signal is used to study events from the CSV and PCLV. An alternative approach has to be used for CIV events due the complete loss of the charge signal. For this, a data-driven convolutional neural network position reconstruction algorithm [73] is employed using only the PMT hit pattern of the S1 signal (S1-only position reconstruction). For $S1 > 20\,000$ PE, this algorithm can achieve a position reconstruction resolution of about 2 cm in x , y and z . For smaller

light signals, the resolution decreases. Thus, alpha events from the ^{222}Rn chain with an S1 signal above 40 000 PE and directional high energy γ -rays with an S1 area above 25 000 PE provided by the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ calibration source are studied in the following. First, the γ -rays are examined to provide a sensitive check of the size of the charge loss volume and its CSF profile. Thereafter, the spatial distribution of events with charge loss is further investigated using alpha events from background data. Finally, a modification of the definition of the FV is proposed, which efficiently rejects PCLV events. At the end of each study, the observations are interpreted regarding the extent of the CIV and PCLV. In the last section, the results of the two studies are summarized and compared.

3.2 Studying the Charge Insensitive Volume with AmBe Calibration Data

The expected CIV and PCLV in the TPC are investigated with 2.2 MeV (^2H line) and 4.4 MeV (^{12}C line) γ -rays from the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ calibration source. These high-energy γ -rays are of interest because they mostly produce ERs very close to the TPC wall where the CIV and PCLV are expected. Additionally, a large range of the CSF down to $\sim 0.01\%$ can be studied due to the large light signals above 10^6 PE. The three source positions used for this study *top*, *bottom 1* and *bottom 2* are characterized in table 2.1.

3.2.1 Event Selection

A *DAQ veto cut* is applied to all data to discard time intervals, which are close to a veto signal from one of the detectors. Additionally, a selection of data quality cuts is applied. These are briefly discussed in the following for the selection of PCLV candidates and subsequently for the selection of CIV candidates.

Partial Charge Loss Volume Candidates

In this part of the study, events from the two high-energy γ -rays with lower-than-expected charge signals are examined. Since these events only lost part of their S2 signal, the information of the S2 signal can be used to select single scatter ERs with correctly matched S1 and S2 signals. Likewise, the position in z and θ of an event is correctly reconstructed by the standard reconstruction algorithm described in section 2.4.2. Depending on the extent of the CIV, the position in r can be biased due to the flawed field distortion correction. Most of the cuts applied to PCLV candidates are modifications of the cuts developed and characterized for XENON1T [54]. Events with correctly matched S1 and S2 signals are selected based on parameter correlations expected for physical events. For this, the fraction of the S1 signal seen by the top PMT array, referred to as *S1 Area Fraction Top* (S1 AFT), is examined. S1 AFT is maximal for events at the top of the TPC and decreases for events at lower

Figure 3.3: Illustration of the selection of partial charge loss volume (PCLV) candidates for the ^2H (2.2 MeV) and ^{12}C (4.4 MeV) γ -rays from the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ calibration source. The plots show the same dataset as a 2D-histogram (left) and as a scatter plot with the deviation from the sources z position Δz (right). PCLV candidates have the same cS1 but a smaller cS2 signal compared to the main population (ellipse). The dotted black lines indicate regions of constant charge survival fraction (100 %, 50 %, 25 %, 10 %, and 1 % are shown). The black box indicates the region of interest with a charge survival fraction below 25 %. One can see that the events in this region predominantly occur below the sources' position in z .

z due to the detector geometry (see fig. 2.6 left). It is therefore an S2-independent measure of the interaction depth z and can be used to assess whether S1 and S2 signals are correctly matched. One requires that S1 AFT and the measured drift time of the charge signal are anti-correlated, assuming a correct match of the two signals. Moreover, a population of events with particularly low S1 AFT, which can be related to events below the cathode, is discarded. Another requirement to select correctly matched S1 and S2 signals is based on the width of the charge signal. It is compared to the expected broadening due to diffusion for a given size of the S2 signal and its reconstructed drift time. If the S2 is wider or narrower than expected, the event is discarded. This selection criterion can additionally remove multiple scatter events for which the charge signals are merged. To target multiple scatter events for which the S2 signals are not merged, events with an alternative S2 signal with large area are discarded. For this analysis, a fiducial volume selection is only applied via z . Events with $-145 \text{ cm} < z < -7.5 \text{ cm}$ are selected. This removes, for example, events with large S1 losses due to electrode shadowing. Finally, events with a considerable difference between the positions reconstructed by the three algorithms discussed in section 2.4.2 are discarded.

Events from ^2H and ^{12}C γ -rays are selected based on their corrected S1 size. The bounds $cS1 \in [13\,500, 19\,500]$ for ^2H and $cS1 \in [28\,000, 35\,500]$ for ^{12}C are chosen to

include most of the events in the main population. In the cS1-region of the ^2H line, events from the 2.6 MeV γ -ray from ^{208}Tl from external material background leak into the selection. Within these ranges of cS1, PCLV candidates are selected based on their estimated CSF. For each event, the CSF can be estimated based on the size of $\text{cS2}_{\text{observed}}$ and the cS2 size expected without any charge loss $\langle \text{cS2}_{\text{full}} \rangle$

$$\text{CSF} = \frac{\text{cS2}_{\text{observed}}}{\langle \text{cS2}_{\text{full}} \rangle}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $\langle \text{cS2}_{\text{full}} \rangle$ is approximated by the mode of the distribution in cS2 for a given slice in cS1. The selection of ^2H and ^{12}C PCLV candidates is illustrated in fig. 3.3. In the shown energy region, the ER band approximately follows a linear function with a slope of 67 PE/PE. Gamma-ray events with correctly reconstructed cS1, which lost half of the charge signal, are accordingly distributed on a linear function with half of the slope. From fig. 3.3 (right) one can see that the events with lower cS2 and thus lower CSF are predominantly located below the source. The selections of events with $\text{CSF} < 25\%$ are indicated by two black boxes in the plot. To account for the average increase of cS2 size with cS1, the estimation of the CSF for each event is performed in $\text{cS2}/\text{cS1}$. One can see in fig. 3.3 (left) that the centers of the ellipses deviate slightly from the linear function. Therefore, the mode of the distribution in $\log_{10}(\text{cS2}/\text{cS1})$ is obtained individually for each γ -line and each source position. Events with $\text{CSF} < 50\%$ are considered PCLV candidates.

Charge Insensitive Volume Candidates

Many data quality cuts are defined based on information of the S2 signal. Thus, for the study of events without charge signal, one must define alternative selection criteria. Many of the decision boundaries of the criteria discussed below are defined based on the distribution of events with correctly matched S1 and S2 signals after applying the data quality cuts available for them.

Events from within the gas phase are discarded by limiting the width of the S1 signal. Another S1 quality cut is defined based on the correlation of the width and the rise time of S1 signals. For the particular field in XENONnT, it was observed that ERs induced by γ - and β -rays have a broader S1 signal compared to alpha particle interactions. This characteristic is used to discriminate between the two types of events. The discrimination is relevant for CIV candidates since ^2H and ^{12}C events are selected based on their uncorrected S1 signal, which has a broader distribution compared to the corrected S1 signal used for the event selection of PCLV candidates. This way, alpha events can leak into the selection of the γ -ray events. The regions $\text{S1} \in [10\,000, 22\,000]$ for ^2H and $\text{S1} \in [22\,000, 42\,000]$ for ^{12}C are defined based on the S1 distribution of events with correctly matched S1 and S2. To discard multiple scatter events, a cut is defined analogously to the one discussed above based on the alternative S2 signal and applied thereafter.

If the entire charge of an event is lost to the wall, the detected S1 signal is matched with a “random” S2 signal, which is not related to the number of electron-ion pairs

Figure 3.4: Gamma-ray events with randomly matched S2 signal (red) are selected based on their very short reconstructed drift time $t_{\text{drift}} < 20 \mu\text{s}$. For events with correctly matched S1 and S2, the fraction of the S1 signal seen by the top PMT array (S1 AFT) is anti-correlated with the drift time. The location of these events is indicated by the gray band.

produced by the interaction. Such events can be identified by the fact that they do not follow the anti-correlated relationship between t_{drift} and S1 AFT. Figure 3.4 shows the distribution of events in t_{drift} and S1 AFT after applying the aforementioned cuts. The anti-correlated region of correctly matched S1 and S2 signals is indicated in gray. Events that lie outside this region are potential events from within the CIV. One can see that most of these events have a very low reconstructed drift time $t_{\text{drift}} < 20 \mu\text{s}$. It was demonstrated that for large S1 signals, many of the randomly matched S2 signals are after-pulses that are misclassified as S2 signals [74]. Such after-pulses can occur if residual gas is present in a PMT. If a photon from the S1 signal hits the photocathode of a PMT, a photo-electron is freed and accelerated towards the first dynode of the PMT. If residual gas is present, the electron can ionize atoms or molecules along its trajectory. These positively charged ions are then accelerated towards the photocathode and can liberate further electrons which cause an after-pulse with typical delay times of a few microseconds after the recorded S1 signal. To ensure that no events with correctly matched S1 and S2 signals are included, only events with $t_{\text{drift}} < 20 \mu\text{s}$ and $cS2 < 10^4$ PE are selected as CIV candidates.

For the CIV candidates, the position is obtained with the S1-only position reconstruction algorithm. The S1 signal of ${}^2\text{H}$ γ -rays is too low to achieve a reasonable position resolution. For $z < -135$ cm, events from the unavoidable charge insensitive region below the cathode are reconstructed. Since these events cannot be distinguished from the CIV under study, the region is excluded from the analysis.

3.2.2 Spatial Distribution of Partial Charge Loss Candidates

The distribution of PCLV candidates in the TPC is studied for the three positions of the source. The distribution in θ , r^2 and z is shown for the ^2H line and the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source at the position *bottom 2* in fig. 3.5. The conclusions drawn from the spatial distribution are the same for both γ -lines and all three source positions. In the scatter plots as well as in the projected histograms in each dimension, events of the full range in CSF, which are mainly from the CSV, are shown in gray and PCLV candidates are colored. The fraction of the PCLV candidates from the total distribution is plotted for each dimension. One can see in all plots, that PCLV candidates do not follow the distribution of the main population. The maximum of the total distribution in z is approximately at the z position of the source. For PCLV candidates, in contrast, the distribution has a maximum below $z = -140$ cm, where they account for about 30% of all events. The fraction of PCLV candidates drops to about 8% at $z = -110$ cm and then slowly decreases further towards zero at the top of the TPC. Most PCLV candidates are reconstructed at large radii outside the TPC, where they account for up to 100% of the total distribution. The distribution of PCLV candidates has a maximum at the radius of the TPC and then quickly drops towards the center of the TPC. Inside the nominal 4t FV defined in [75], a leakage of PCLV candidates on the level of 1% of the total distribution is observed. Some of these could be multiple scatter events not discarded by the cuts. The distribution of PCLV candidates in θ shows a strong clustering at the panels of the TPC (between the pillars). In the scatter plots, the PCLV candidates are colored according to their CSF, which ranges from 50% down to 0.01%. For the events with the lowest CSF, one can see an enhanced clustering at the panels and in the lower and outer part of the TPC.

3.2.3 Comparison of Data and Field Simulation

The approximate distribution of PCLV and CIV events expected from the field simulation is obtained to verify whether the observed data is consistent with it. Due to a non-uniform shielding of the γ -rays in θ and z , the distribution of the interactions in the TPC is not trivial. The approximate distribution is obtained by evaluating the CSF maps (fig. 3.2) at the reconstructed positions of the data with any charge signal. In this simplification, one assumes that the reconstructed position coincides with the position of interaction. Particularly close to the wall, however, the deviation of the two positions can be of the order of a few centimeters due to a worse position reconstruction uncertainty and a bias due to the field distortion correction. However, for a qualitative study, this approach is viable.

The distributions of PCLV candidates in z are compared to the expected distributions from the field simulation in slices of CSF as shown in fig. 3.6 for ^2H events. For the *top* position (first column), less PCLV candidates are found at the top of the TPC ($z > -40$ cm) in all slices with CSF $> 1\%$ (first three rows). The smallest slice in CSF has too low statistics to make a statement. For the two measurements with the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source at the bottom positions (second and third column), the

Figure 3.5: Distribution of ${}^2\text{H}$ gamma events in the TPC for the ${}^{241}\text{AmBe}$ calibration source at position *bottom 2*. The top panels show scatter plots of all ${}^2\text{H}$ γ -ray events (gray) and the partial charge loss volume (PCLV) candidates (colored) in z versus θ and z versus r^2 . To the right, the histogram in z of all events (gray) and the PCLV candidates (blue) as well as the binwise fraction of the PCLV candidates from the total distribution is shown. Similar plots are shown in the lower panels for θ and r^2 . The color of the PCLV candidates indicates the estimated charge survival fraction of each event.

Figure 3.6: Comparison of the z -distributions of partial charge loss volume (PCLV) candidates (blue) and the approximate distribution expected from field simulation (gray) for ^{241}H γ -ray events. The distributions are shown for the three positions of the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ source (columns) and in three slices of estimated charge survival fraction (CSF, rows). The panels to the left of each histogram show the residuals.

Figure 3.7: Similar to fig. 3.6 but for ^{12}C γ -ray events. The bottom panel shows the z -distribution of charge insensitive volume (CIV) candidates. Below $z = -135$ cm, CIV candidates cannot be distinguished from the numerous events from the region below the cathode of the detector. Therefore, this region is excluded from the analysis.

z -distributions are similar. Less PCLV candidates are seen in the data in multiple bins for the upper two thirds of the TPC ($z > -100$ cm). The lack of events extends even further down to $z > -125$ cm for $1\% < \text{CSF} < 10\%$ (third row). For $\text{CSF} > 1\%$ (top three rows), an excess of PCLV candidates is observed in the bottom part of the TPC ($z < -125$ cm). The histograms of $0.01\% < \text{CSF} < 1\%$ (fourth row), show a lack of PCLV candidates compared to the simulation in most bins.

The z -distribution of PCLV and CIV candidates for ^{12}C events is shown in fig. 3.7. Due to the lower statistics of ^{12}C compared to ^2H events, the PCLV candidates are not presented in slices of CSF. Still, one can see a similar behavior as observed for the ^2H γ -rays. In the upper part of the TPC ($z > -125$ cm), a lack of events is observed. Only in the lowest bins of the data with bottom source position an excess of PCLV candidates can be seen. The distribution of CIV candidates spikes at the bottom of the TPC and shows almost no events for $z > -115$ cm. From the field simulation, in turn, a few hundred CIV candidates are expected in this region. The deviation is best visible for the *top* position of the source. An excess of CIV candidates can be found at the bottom of the TPC for $z < -120$ cm.

For ^2H events, the S1 signal is too small to achieve a reasonable resolution with

the S1-only position reconstruction algorithm. Therefore, the distribution of ^2H CIV candidates in the TPC could not be evaluated. However, an increase of CIV candidates with low values of S1 AFT, which corresponds to events at the bottom of the TPC, was observed in the data.

3.2.4 Interpretation of the Results

The observation of CIV candidates and PCLV candidates with a wide range of CSF down to the detection limit of S2 signals at about $\text{CSF} = 0.01\%$ confirms the existence of the corresponding charge loss volumes in the TPC. From the z -distribution of the data one can conclude that the CIV and PCLV are largest at the bottom of the TPC, in particular below $z = -115\text{ cm}$. However, a smaller PCLV extends along the entire wall of the TPC. The clustering of PCLV candidates observed at the angular positions of the panels hints towards a PCLV that is larger at the panels compared to the pillars. A quantitative analysis of this behavior is discussed in section 3.3.3.

Compared to the approximate expectation from the field simulation, the calibration campaigns at the three positions indicated that the PCLV containing the smallest observable signals with $0.01\% < \text{CSF} < 1\%$ is smaller than expected. For larger signals with $\text{CSF} > 1\%$, a smaller PCLV is observed for the upper two thirds of the TPC and a larger PCLV in the lower $\sim 25\text{ cm}$. The analysis of ^{12}C CIV candidates indicates a smaller CIV for the upper $\sim 80\%$ of the TPC and a larger CIV at the bottom.

The study of $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ data is well-suited to obtain a qualitative picture of the charge loss volume due to the high statistics of events in the interesting region of the TPC. However, to quantify the CIV and PCLV, a spatially uniform source is advantageous, which is pursued in section 3.3.

3.3 Studying the Charge Insensitive Volume with Alpha Background Data

A uniformly distributed source is best suited to map the distribution and size of the PCLV and CIV in the TPC. For this purpose, alpha decays from ^{222}Rn with an energy of 5.5 MeV ^{218}Po with an energy of 6.0 MeV are selected in background data. Besides those, alpha events from the decay of ^{210}Po with an energy of 5.3 MeV , which are accumulated on the PTFE walls, are examined to study the outermost part of the CIV and PCLV.

3.3.1 Event Selection

Prior to the selection of ^{210}Po , ^{222}Rn , and ^{218}Po alpha events, two data quality cuts are applied. Single scatter events are selected based on the size of a potential alternative S2 signal as discussed in section 3.2.1. To discriminate alpha events from ERs, the

same selection based on the width of S1 signals as discussed in section 3.2.1 is inverted to select alpha events instead of rejecting them.

Then, alpha events from the decays of ^{210}Po , ^{222}Rn , and ^{218}Po are selected based on the size of the S1 signal. The selection boundaries in S1 are defined as functions of S1 AFT, which is a measure of the interaction depth z of an event. This accounts for the strong dependence of the S1 size on z . As one can see in fig. 3.8 a, the size of S1 for constant deposited energy increases with decreasing S1 AFT, which corresponds to a deeper position in the TPC. For ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po events, one can see in fig. 3.8 b that the S1 size additionally depends on the radius r of the interaction. The position dependence of the S1 signal is discussed in section 2.4.3 and is usually corrected for. However, a correctly matched S2 signal is assumed for this correction. Thus, it is not useful for selecting CIV candidates, which have a randomly matched S2 signals. As discussed later, most ^{210}Po events have randomly matched S2 signals. Therefore, no correlation is seen between the size of S1 and the radius reconstructed using the S2 signal. Figure 3.8 c shows the corrected size of the matched S2 signal on the color axis. ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po events mainly have cS2 sizes above 10 000 PE as it is expected from alpha particle interactions. ^{210}Po events, in turn, mainly have S2 signals of about 1000 PE, primarily from incorrectly classified peaks. Based on fig. 3.8 a-c, three decision boundaries are defined to select ^{210}Po and $^{222}\text{Rn}/^{218}\text{Po}$ events. Each boundary, shown as black lines in fig. 3.8, is defined as the sum of three exponential functions in S1. In addition, a selection of S1 AFT < 0.57 is applied, which contains all events in the liquid phase of the TPC. Due to the proximity of the two selected bands, a selection bias in z and r cannot be excluded. A broadening of the bands in S1 is visible for the lowest and highest values of the selected S1 AFT, which corresponds to events at the very top and the very bottom of the TPC. Here, the large S1 signal causes the ADCs (analog-to-digital-converters) used for PMT readout to saturate. The number of saturated ADC channels is shown on the color axis of fig. 3.8 d. To account for the worse selection induced by the broadening of the S1 distribution at the top and at the bottom of the TPC, these regions are excluded from the analysis. For this, $-140\text{ cm} < z < -5\text{ cm}$ is selected, where z is defined according to the respective appropriate position reconstruction algorithms for CIV, PCLV, and CSV candidates.

Correctly Matched S2 and Randomly Matched S2 Events

Events with correctly matched S1 and S2 signals are selected by requiring anti-correlation of the measured drift time and the S1 AFT as discussed in section 3.2.1. Quantile-based cut boundaries in S1 AFT as a function of the drift time are defined to achieve a higher cut acceptance of events with saturated ADC channels. The decision boundaries are shown in fig. 3.9.

Events outside the boundaries are most likely events with a randomly matched S2 signal. As one can see in fig. 3.9 (left), most of them have reconstructed drift times below $20\text{ }\mu\text{s}$. As discussed in section 3.2.1, these events are mainly after-pulses with reconstructed charge signals below 10 000 PE, which are induced by the large S1

Figure 3.8: Selection of alpha events from the decays of ^{210}Po events and ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po . The S1 signal and the fraction of it seen by the top PMT array (S1 AFT) of the same data is shown in all four panels. The color axis shows different interesting parameters used to define the selection boundaries shown in black. While ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po have mostly a correctly matched S2 signal, ^{210}Po events are mainly reconstructed at random positions r based on randomly matched small S2 signals. At low values of S1 AFT, corresponding to a position in the lower part of the TPC, many PMT channels are saturated, which affects the selection.

Figure 3.9: Selection of alpha events with correctly and randomly matched charge signals. **Left:** The selection is based on the fraction of the S1 signal seen by the top PMT array (S1 AFT) and the reconstructed drift time. Events with drift times below $20\ \mu\text{s}$ show no anti-correlation of the two quantities and are thus classified as events with randomly matched S2. **Right:** Events with randomly matched S2 are further subdivided into events with correctly matched alternative S2 (AS2) and events with randomly matched AS2 signals. For this, the drift time and size of the AS2 signal is considered.

signals of alpha particle interactions. Events with $t_{\text{drift}} < 20\ \mu\text{s}$ and $\text{cS2} < 10\ 000\ \text{PE}$ are classified as events with randomly matched S2 (referred to as *random S2 events*). To obtain a clean population of events with correctly matched S2 (referred to as *matched S2 events*), $t_{\text{drift}} > 20\ \mu\text{s}$ is required in addition to the anti-correlation selection.

However, a fraction of the events with randomly matched S2 signals does have a physical charge signal. If the charge loss of an event is so large that the physical S2 is smaller than the reconstructed S2 of an after-pulse, the after-pulse is classified as the main S2 signal of the event and the physical S2 is only classified as the alternative S2 signal (AS2). One can recover such events with randomly matched S2 signal but correctly matched AS2 signal (referred to as *random S2, matched AS2 events*) based on the anti-correlation of S1 AFT and the drift time of the AS2 interaction $t_{\text{drift AS2}}$ as shown in fig. 3.9 (right). The detection threshold of 200 PE is applied for the corrected AS2 size of *random S2, matched AS2 events*. Events with randomly matched S2 and randomly matched AS2 signals (*random S2, random AS2 events*) are selected as events with a corrected AS2 area below 200 PE and $t_{\text{drift AS2}} < 320\ \mu\text{s}$ in addition to the selections of the random S2 events.

Charge Loss Classification

Events with correctly matched S2 or AS2 either originate from the CSV or the PCLV. The separation of the two is done based on the corrected S2 size of the physical S2 signal, $\text{cS2}_{\text{physical}}$, which corresponds to the cS2 for *matched S2* events and the alternative cS2 for *random S2, matched AS2* events. The CSF of each event is estimated with

Figure 3.10: Subdivision of events with correctly matched charge signals into charge sensitive volume (CSV) and partial charge loss volume (PCLV) candidates in physical cS2. For *matched S2* events, this corresponds to the corrected S2 size. For *random S2, matched AS2* events, the size of the corrected AS2 signal is plotted.

eq. (3.1) using $\langle cS2_{\text{full}} \rangle = 27\,000$ PE. Events with $13\,500 \text{ PE} < cS2_{\text{physical}} < 56\,000 \text{ PE}$ are classified as CSV candidates. The lower bound corresponds to an estimated CSF of 50% and events with $cS2_{\text{physical}}$ below this value are PCLV candidates. The distribution of the two alpha populations in $cS2_{\text{physical}}$ and the selection of CSV and PCLV candidates are shown in fig. 3.10. Events with $cS2_{\text{physical}} > 100\,000$ PE that are visible in the histogram are likely leakage events from a population with large cS2 and lower S1 as one can see in fig. 3.8 c. The origin of these events was not identified. *Random S2, matched AS2* events are considered CIV candidates.

3.3.2 Spatial Distribution in the TPC

The location of CSV, PCLV, and CIV candidates in the TPC is studied for ^{210}Po , ^{222}Rn , and ^{218}Po events. For CSV and PCLV candidates, the standard position reconstruction algorithm discussed in section 2.4.2 based on the physical charge signal is used. For CIV candidates, the position is obtained with the S1-only position reconstruction algorithm. The distribution in z and θ of CSV, PCLV and CIV candidates is shown for ^{210}Po events in fig. 3.11 and for ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po events in fig. 3.12. Only events with $r^2 > 3000 \text{ cm}^2$ are shown in the plots, which mainly reduces the number of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po CSV candidates. The colors indicate the classification into CSV, PCLV, and CIV candidates. Below each scatter plot, the projected histogram in θ and the fraction of each component of the total number of events for a given θ are shown. For the projection plots in θ , only events with $-140 \text{ cm} < z < -5 \text{ cm}$ are selected. Hashed gray regions in θ indicate the position of PTFE pillars at the inner surface of the TPC. To the right of each scatter plot, the histogram and fractions in z are shown.

The total distribution of ^{210}Po events is not uniform in either z or θ . In the scatter

plot, multiple clusters of ^{210}Po events can be seen. These seem to be connected over the entire height of the TPC but are apparently not constrained by the location of the PTFE pillars and panels. The reason for the non-uniformity of the distribution is not understood. In a small region at the top of the TPC, most ^{210}Po events are PCLV candidates and also an increase of CSV candidates can be seen. Apart from this, most ^{210}Po events are CIV candidates, with a fraction that approaches 100% towards the bottom of the TPC. The projected distribution in θ shows that CSV and PCLV candidates are mostly accumulated at the pillars, while the fraction of CIV candidates is larger at the panels.

For ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po , the total distribution of events with $r^2 > 3000 \text{ cm}^2$ is approximately uniform in z and θ . Most of the events are CSV candidates throughout the entire TPC. A slight increase of CIV candidates is visible at the bottom of the TPC. PCLV and CIV candidates often appear in small clusters in θ and z , predominantly at angles corresponding to the position of the PTFE panels.

3.3.3 Comparison of Data and Field Simulation

Analogous to section 3.2.3, the approximate distribution of PCLV and CIV events expected from the field simulation is obtained to verify whether the observed data is consistent with it. For this, the spatial distribution of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha particle interactions is modeled as a uniform distribution in r^2 , θ , and z . The distribution in z and θ of ^{210}Po events is assumed to be uniform as well. Its distribution in r^2 is modeled by one half of a Gaussian centered at the TPC wall with a standard deviation corresponding to the range of alpha particles in LXe of $46 \mu\text{m}$ under the continuous slowing down approximation (CSDA) [76]. For ^{210}Po , uniformity in θ and z is not given, as observed in fig. 3.11. Also, the distribution in r^2 is a rough estimate of the actual distribution, which can only be obtained by simulation. Despite the simplifications, however, it is possible to qualitatively study the expected distribution of ^{210}Po events.

The fraction of the number of events of CSV, PCLV, and CIV candidates from the total number of events within $-140 \text{ cm} < z < -5 \text{ cm}$ and with $r^2 > 3000 \text{ cm}^2$ is compared to the approximate expected values from the field simulation. The PCLV candidates are subdivided into events with $\text{CSF} < 3.7\%$ and events with $\text{CSF} > 3.7\%$. This boundary corresponds to an observed physical cS2 size of 1000 PE and thus roughly separates the dataset into PCLV candidates with *matched S2* and those with *random S2*, *matched AS2* (see fig. 3.10). The fractions observed in data and expected from simulation are shown in fig. 3.13. The right right panel shows the corresponding residuals, for which only the binomial errors of the data points are considered. The systematic error of the the simulation is not taken into account, but in particular for ^{210}Po it is likely the dominant term. Some residuals are beyond 10σ . Despite these large deviations, one can state that the order of magnitude of the fractions agrees for simulation and data in all categories. For ^{210}Po , ^{222}Rn , and ^{218}Po , the fraction of CSV candidates in data is lower than expected and the fraction of events with $\text{CSF} < 3.7\%$ is larger than expected from simulations. From the measured fraction of PCLV and

Figure 3.11: Distribution of ^{210}Po alpha events in the TPC. The scatter plot shows the location of all events with $r^2 > 3000 \text{ cm}^2$ in θ and z . To the right and below, the projected histograms of the total distribution and the binwise fraction of GSV, PCLV and CIV candidates from the total distribution are shown. The colors in all plots indicate the classification as GSV, PCLV, and CIV candidates.

Figure 3.12: Same as fig. 3.11 but for ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events.

CIV candidates from all ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po events with $r^2 > 3000 \text{ cm}^2$ one can estimate the insensitive mass in the range $-140 \text{ cm} < z < -5 \text{ cm}$ of $m_{\text{CIV}} = (120 \pm 4) \text{ kg}$ and the mass of the PCLV of $m_{\text{PCLV}} = (56 \pm 3) \text{ kg}$. They are respectively a factor 2.9 and 1.3 larger than the values expected from field simulations $m_{\text{CIV}}^{\text{sim}} = 42 \text{ kg}$ and $m_{\text{PCLV}}^{\text{sim}} = 44 \text{ kg}$. The fraction of the volume exhibiting more than 50% charge loss related to the total volume can be estimated as $(3.31 \pm 0.09) \%$.

The clustering of PCLV and CIV candidates at the pillars (panels) observed for ^{210}Po (^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po) alpha events in fig. 3.11 (fig. 3.12) is quantified. For this, the fraction of events located at the pillars, referred to as *pillar fraction*, is plotted in fig. 3.14 for ^{210}Po (top) and ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po (bottom). The value expected for θ -independent CIV and PCLV is given by the fraction of the pillar surface area with respect to the total PTFE surface area ($\sim 32 \%$) and shown as a dark blue vertical line in the plots. The expected values from the field simulation are shown in light blue. As in fig. 3.13, the right panels show the residuals, where only the binomial errors of the data points are considered. For ^{210}Po CSV and PCLV candidates, the pillar fraction is larger than expected from a θ -independent charge loss volume, which corresponds to the observed clustering of events at the pillars. For CIV candidates, the pillar fraction is below the θ -independent expectation, indicating clustering at the PTFE panels. The agreement with both the θ -independent expectation and the expectation from the field simulation is poor, which can be attributed to the stated non-uniform distribution of ^{210}Po events in θ and z . For ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po , the pillar fraction is below the θ -independent expectation. The fraction decreases with decreasing CSF, which corresponds to increasing clustering at the panels for events of higher charge loss. The agreement of the data is not sufficiently good with either of the models to favor one over the other.

Given the spatially uniform distribution of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events, the number of CIV and PCLV candidates in a slice of z is directly related to the size of the volumes in that region. The distribution of CSV, PCLV, and CIV candidates in z are shown for the pillars and panels separately in fig. 3.15. For CSV candidates (first row), the distribution in z is approximately uniform for pillars and panels. The PCLV candidates (second row) at the pillars show a maximum at the top of the TPC, while at the panels they are mostly distributed at the bottom of the TPC with one exception for the largest bin with $z = -70 \text{ cm}$ and $z = -75 \text{ cm}$. Most CIV candidates are located at the bottom of the TPC. At the panels, many CIV candidates are also observed at $z = -40 \text{ cm}$ and $z = -90 \text{ cm}$.

The comparison with the distribution expected from the field simulation (gray) reveals the regions responsible for the larger-than-expected masses of CIV and PCLV. For PCLV candidates, the bin at the panels between $z = -70 \text{ cm}$ and $z = -75 \text{ cm}$ corresponds to an excess of almost 4σ . At the pillars, an excess of events can be observed for four consecutive bins at the top of the TPC ($z > -25 \text{ cm}$). The CIV candidates at the panels exceed the simulation in all bins. In the central region ($-80 \text{ cm} < z < -40 \text{ cm}$) and at the bottom ($z < -115 \text{ cm}$), individual bins exceed the simulation by more than 3σ . Looking at fig. 3.12, this can mainly be attributed to two clusters of CIV candidates at the panels between $-1.92 \text{ rad} < \theta < -1.74 \text{ rad}$

Figure 3.13: Fraction of the total number of events in slices of the reconstructed charge survival fraction (CSF) for ^{210}Po (top), and ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events (bottom). The fraction of the data is indicated in gray and the blue vertical lines show the expectation from the field simulations. The residual of data and simulation is shown in the right panel.

Figure 3.14: Fraction of the number of events at the pillars in slices of the reconstructed charge survival fraction (CSF) for ^{210}Po (top), and ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events (bottom). The fraction of the data is indicated in gray and the light blue vertical lines show the approximated expectation from the field simulations. The expected fraction for a uniform distribution in θ is shown as a dark blue vertical line. The residual of data and simulation is shown in the right panel.

and $0.17 \text{ rad} < \theta < 0.35 \text{ rad}$. Also for the CIV candidates at the pillars, an excess of events in the data is seen at the bottom of the TPC ($z < -130 \text{ cm}$).

3.3.4 Interpretation of the Results

From the spatially uniform decays of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po , a map of the PCLV and CIV at the pillars and panels is obtained. From the distribution in z , one can derive that the CIV is largest at the bottom of the TPC and that both PCLV and CIV extend along the entire wall of the TPC. The estimated masses exceed the expectations from simulation. For the CIV, it is almost three times larger, which is mainly due to an excess of CIV candidates at the panels and in particular below $z = -125 \text{ cm}$. The analysis of ^{210}Po from the surface of the TPC wall confirms the observation of a charge loss volume that is larger at the bottom compared to the top.

The pillar fractions found in data do not agree with the simulation but still all data hints towards a larger PCLV and CIV at the panels compared to the pillars. Due to the short range of alpha particles in LXe of below $50 \mu\text{m}$, ^{210}Po events would barely reach the region of partial charge loss at the panels, in particular at the bottom of the TPC, causing a clustering of CSV and PCLV candidates at the pillars. Given their short range, the observation of ^{210}Po CSV candidates at the pillars in the upper part of the TPC is a hint for a very small CIV at this location. In contrast to ^{210}Po alphas, which only reach part of the charge loss volume, ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po events are spatially uniformly distributed in the CSV, PCLV, and CIV. In this case, a the larger PCLV and CIV at the panels leads to an increased rate of events with charge loss at the panels. The same is true for the high-energy γ -rays discussed in section 3.2, which reach far into the TPC. The observation that the excess of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po CIV candidates in the central region is mainly caused by two of the 24 panels indicates that the charge loss volume exhibits a more complex structure in θ .

Qualitatively, the conclusions drawn from the studies of $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ γ -rays and alpha particle interactions agree. However, for ^2H events, a smaller-than-expected PCLV with $\text{CSF} > 1\%$ was stated in the upper part of the TPC while for ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events the z -distributions for $\text{CSF} > 0.7\%$ are mostly compatible with the simulation or exceed them. This deviation might be explained by the limitations of the approximate method for obtaining the distribution expected from simulation. Also, a more complex structure of the charge loss volume in θ can cause a mismatch between the two studies since the $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ calibration data does not cover all angles of the TPC.

3.3.5 Choice of a Fiducial Volume

The uniformly distributed alpha events are used in the previous sections to develop a data-driven map of the CIV and PCLV. However, the statistics of this map is not sufficiently high to construct a complete data-driven model in z , CSF , θ and r that could for example be used in the statistical inference of the data. An alternative approach to modeling the CIV and PCLV is to define a fiducial volume to exclude

Figure 3.15: Distribution in z of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events. The distribution of charge sensitive volume (CSV) candidates (top), partial charge loss volume (PCLV) candidates (middle), and charge insensitive volume (CIV) candidates (bottom) is shown for events at the pillars (left) and panels (right). Only events from the outermost part of the TPC with $r^2 > 3000 \text{ cm}^2$ are plotted. In each histogram, the approximated expected distribution from field simulation is shown in gray. The residuals are shown to the right (left) of the histogram of the pillars (panels).

Figure 3.16: Location of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po partial charge loss volume candidates with $\text{cS2}_{\text{physical}} < 1000$ PE. The optimal fiducial volume only discards about half of the events (left). The fiducial volume is modified by additionally discarding events with $r^2 > 3400$ cm^2 , which greatly improves the efficiency.

regions containing events with impaired S2 signals due to partial charge loss. One example of the rejection efficiency for different FVs is shown in fig. 3.16 for ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po PCLV candidates with $\text{CSF} < 3.7\%$, which corresponds to cS2 signals below 1000 PE. For such small signals, the large radial position reconstruction uncertainty causes considerable leakage of events into the inner part of the TPC. The “optimal FV” shown in the plot was optimized based on various inputs from other analyses performed by members of the collaboration, including the surface background model. With this FV one can only reject $\epsilon = (47.3^{+5.4}_{-4.9})\%$ of the PCLV candidates. The FV is modified by introducing a maximum radius r_{max}^2 of 3400 cm^2 , which greatly improves the rejection efficiency to $\epsilon = (89.0^{+3.4}_{-2.9})\%$ (fig. 3.16 right). The three events with $r^2 < 2000$ cm^2 have a charge signal close to the threshold of 200 PE. Therefore, it is likely that these are events with randomly matched S2 that happen to meet the correlation criteria imposed on the PCLV candidates.

When choosing r_{max}^2 , the increase in rejection efficiency at smaller r_{max}^2 must be weighed against the associated loss of exposure due to the lower fiducial mass. Both values are plotted in fig. 3.17. The asymmetric errors required for efficiencies close to 100% are obtained with a Bayesian approach following [77]. One can see that in particular the rejection efficiency of PCLV candidates with $\text{cS2} < 1000$ PE can be improved strongly by modifying the FV. A rejection efficiency of more than 85% for all PCLV candidates can be achieved with a maximum radius of $r_{\text{max}}^2 = 3400$ cm^2 or $r \simeq 58$ cm, while maintaining a nominal fiducial mass slightly above 4 t, which is the fiducial mass used in the sensitivity studies for XENONnT [15].

Figure 3.17: Efficiency to reject various alpha events by means of a modified fiducial volume as a function of the maximum radius r_{\max}^2 . The lower panel shows the corresponding nominal fiducial mass.

3.4 Summary of the Results and Further Studies

In this study, the spatial distributions of events that suffer from partial or complete charge loss were examined using directional \sim MeV γ -rays from an $^{241}\text{AmBe}$ calibration source, ^{210}Po alpha events from the inner PTFE surface of the TPC, and uniformly distributed ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events. The distributions of the data are compared to the approximate expected distributions from field simulations to assess whether the observed events with charge loss can be explained by field lines ending at the TPC wall. Despite some tensions between the studies with γ -rays and alpha particles regarding the comparison of data and simulation, some common conclusions can be drawn. Events with partial charge loss signals down to the detection limit as well as events without charge signal are found in the data, which shows that a CIV and an associated PCLV are present in the TPC for SR0. The largest charge loss is observed at the lower outer part of the TPC. A smaller charge loss volume extends across the entire wall of the TPC. The observed angular dependence of the distribution of PCLV and CIV candidates indicates a larger charge loss volume at the PTFE panels compared to the pillars. Moreover, ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po alpha events suggest a more complex structure of the θ -distribution of the charge loss volume.

From the spatially uniform distribution of alpha events, one can estimate an insensitive mass in the range $-140\text{ cm} < z < -5\text{ cm}$ of $m_{\text{CIV}} = (120 \pm 4)\text{ kg}$ and a mass of the PCLV of $m_{\text{PCLV}} = (56 \pm 3)\text{ kg}$, which are both larger than expected from field simulations. The combined mass corresponds to $(3.31 \pm 0.09)\%$ of the LXe in this z -range. This induces a bias to the estimated fiducial mass due to an incorrect field distortion correction. However, all observations rule out a charge loss volume that is much larger than expected from the field simulation. To precisely estimate the effect on the nominal fiducial mass, a complete model of the charge loss volume including the S2 dependence of the boundary between CIV and PCLV is required. Such a model could be included in the field distortion correction algorithm to reduce the positional bias due to a charge loss volume. Furthermore, it could be used to improve the surface background model of XENONnT. To derive a data-driven model, higher statistics of alpha events and a more elaborate separation of ^{210}Po and ^{222}Rn would be required. The latter could be achieved by implementing an S1-only based correction of the S1 signal. To increase the statistics, one could include data from calibration campaigns for the analysis. Further, it might be possible to loosen some of the cuts for the classification regarding the matched or random charge signals. For slices in CSF and separately at the pillars and panels, one could then model the radial distribution of each component based on the number of counts in bins of z , using the spatial uniformity of ^{222}Rn alpha decays. For a detailed analysis of the differences between data and field simulation, the expected spatial distributions of interactions for the various studied sources could be simulated with Monte Carlo methods. Also, the efficiencies of the different cuts used for CSV, PCLV, and CIV candidates should be quantified and considered in the analysis.

For a conservative data analysis and in particular to omit a bias of calibration measurements, a modified FV is proposed, which rejects more than 85% of all PCLV

candidates, while maintaining a nominal fiducial mass above 4 t.

Another interesting observation is that ^{210}Po events are not uniformly distributed on the inner PTFE surface. Understanding the origin of this behavior might allow a targeted reduction of surface background in the future.

4 How Good are our Fits?

For various applications, goodness-of-fit tests are essential statistical tools in the analysis of XENONnT data. For this reason, the performance of different tests and the influence of the binning on the test result were studied with systematic toy-model analyses. In the first section, a brief overview of the concept of goodness of fit is given and the different tests used in this work are introduced.

4.1 Goodness of Fit

Goodness-of-fit (GOF) tests are performed to assess the degree of agreement between experimental data and a fit to the data. The true underlying probability density function (PDF) f of a data set is unknown for experimental data. To extract information from the data, a PDF f_0 is fit to it. In a GOF test, the null hypothesis H_0 that $f = f_0$ is tested against *all possible* alternatives to H_0 . The test is performed based on a test statistic T , which is a function of the data given H_0 . For a specified data set and null hypothesis, it takes a value T_0 . Often, the test statistic is defined such that less agreement results in a larger value. However, this alone is not sufficient to make a statistical statement. The significance of the discrepancy between f and f_0 is quantified by the p-value $p(T_0)$. It corresponds to the probability to find a test statistic with less agreement under the null hypothesis compared to the observed value T_0 . For continuously distributed data, it is defined as

$$p(T_0) = \int_{T_0}^{\infty} g(T|H_0)dT, \quad (4.1)$$

where $g(T|H_0)$ is the PDF of the test statistic under the null hypothesis. A low p-value indicates that *some* alternative hypothesis to H_0 might be true, which is commonly referred to as a “bad fit”. The null hypothesis is rejected at confidence level (C.L.) $1 - \alpha$ if the p-value is smaller than α .

In the context of XENON data analysis, GOF tests are frequently used tools. Such tests are particularly important to verify whether the background models describe calibration data adequately or whether a model or the Monte Carlo method needs to be modified. GOF tests are also used to assess whether the background-only hypothesis describes the background data well. If this is not the case, it indicates that either the background model is incomplete or a signal needs to be included in addition to the background.

4.1.1 The *GOFevaluation* Package

Within the context of this work, software was developed to streamline GOF testing in the XENON collaboration. It is implemented as a Python package [78] and offers the possibility to perform various GOF tests and estimate the corresponding p-values without relying on any asymptotic behavior of the test statistic.

GOF tests can be performed on binned data (section 4.1.2) or on unbinned data (section 4.1.3). Binning the data inherently causes loss of information, so one generally expects unbinned GOF tests to be more powerful. This is particularly true for GOF tests in high dimensional phase space. Due to the large phase space, coarse binning is often required to obtain a sufficient number of counts in each bin. This issue is referred to as the *curse of dimensionality*. However, the advantages of unbinned GOF tests usually come at a comparably high computational cost.

In the following, the methodology of binned and unbinned GOF tests are shortly motivated and the selection of test statistics that are implemented in the *GOFevaluation* package and used in this work are introduced. The methods used for estimating the p-value of a GOF test are discussed in section 4.1.4.

4.1.2 Binned GOF Tests

In binned GOF tests, the data is evaluated as a histogram with k bins. The number of events in the i -th bin n_i is compared to the number of events expected under the null hypothesis in the same bin y_i . The sum over all bins yields the total number of events $N = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i$. In this work, extended maximum likelihood fits are used, in which N is a degree of freedom of the fit. Therefore, the distribution of events among the bins follows Poisson statistics. In this case, the total number of events expected under the null hypothesis $N_0 = \sum_{i=1}^k y_i$ is not constrained to N .

Binned Pearson’s χ^2 Test: One of the most commonly used test statistics for GOF testing is Pearson’s χ^2 [79] defined as

$$\chi_{\text{P}}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(n_i - y_i)^2}{y_i}. \quad (4.2)$$

In literature, this test statistic is often simply referred to as “ χ^2 ”. In the limit of infinite data samples, the distribution of this test statistic follows a chi-square distribution with $k - J - 1$ degrees of freedom, where J is the number of fit parameters¹. A frequently quoted rule of thumb to achieve this asymptotic behavior is that all y_i should be at least 1 while a minimum of 80 % should fulfill $y_i > 5$ [80].

Binned Poisson Likelihood χ^2 Test: Besides this classical definition of χ_{P}^2 , one can construct a variety of other test statistics that asymptotically follow the same

¹for extended maximum likelihood fits, this also includes the rate parameter N_0 .

distribution and are thus also named “ χ^2 ” in statistical literature. One example is a test statistic based on the likelihood ratio for Poisson distributed data [81]. The likelihood ratio is defined as $\lambda = L(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{n})/L(\mathbf{m}; \mathbf{n})$, where $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k)$ are the unknown true values of $\mathbf{n} = (n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ and $L(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{n}) = \prod_{i=1}^k \exp(-y_i) y_i^{n_i} / n_i!$ is the likelihood function for Poisson histograms. The test statistic defined as

$$\chi_\lambda^2 = -2 \ln \lambda = -2 \ln L(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{n}) + 2 \ln L(\mathbf{m}; \mathbf{n}) \quad (4.3)$$

asymptotically follows a chi-square distribution when the null hypothesis is true [82]. The unknown values \mathbf{m} are replaced by their maximum likelihood estimators \mathbf{n} to obtain

$$\chi_\lambda^2 = 2 \sum_{i=1}^k (y_i - n_i + n_i \ln(n_i/y_i)). \quad (4.4)$$

4.1.3 Unbinned GOF Tests

In an unbinned GOF test, the degree of agreement between an unbinned data sample and the fit PDF under the null hypothesis is quantified. For this, often a sample from the PDF of size n_r is generated (referred to as *reference sample*). One could be tempted to simply use the unbinned likelihood of the data as a test statistic for a GOF test. However, as discussed in [83], [84], this approach is flawed and thus should not be used. Two frequently used one-dimensional unbinned GOF tests are the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the Anderson-Darling test. The statistical literature also provides plenty of unbinned GOF tests in multi-dimensional phase space, a selection of which are discussed in [85].

Two-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test: The two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for two one-dimensional samples $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ and $\mathbf{b} = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_m)$ tests whether the underlying probability distributions of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} are the same [86], [87]. The test statistic is defined as the absolute value of the maximal difference between the empirical distribution functions (EDFs) $F_n(x) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{1}_{[-\infty, x]}(a_i)$ and $G_m(x) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbf{1}_{[-\infty, x]}(b_i)$ of the two samples

$$D_{n,m} = \sup_x |F_n(x) - G_m(x)|. \quad (4.5)$$

Here, $\mathbf{1}_A(x)$ is the indicator function of a subset A of a set X . For $x \in X$ it is defined as

$$\mathbf{1}_A(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A. \end{cases} \quad (4.6)$$

For GOF testing, the sample \mathbf{a} of size $n = N$ is the data sample, and a reference sample \mathbf{b} of size $m = n_r \gg n$ is drawn from the fit PDF $f_0(x)$. The definition of the test statistic is illustrated in fig. 4.1. For this, a toy data sample of size $n = N = 50$

is drawn from a normal distribution, and the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is performed for a reference model identical to the model used to generate the data (left panels), and a reference model which is broader and shifted in x (right panels). The normalized histograms of the data sample and the corresponding reference samples are shown in the upper panels. Below that, the EDFs of both samples $F_n(x)$ and $G_m(x)$ are plotted. The maximal distance between $F_n(x)$ and $G_m(x)$, shown as a black line, is the test statistic $D_{n,m}$. The bad fit of the data and the incorrect reference model is expressed by a larger test statistic $D_{n,m}$ compared to the value obtained for the correct model.

Two-Sample Anderson-Darling Test: Another unbinned test based on EDFs is the Anderson-Darling test. It is designed to be more sensitive to deviations at the tails of the EDF as opposed to deviations close to the median, as is the case for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. As one can see in fig. 4.1 for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the discrepancy between the EDF and the cumulative distribution function (CDF) (or between the two EDFs in the two-sample version) necessarily becomes small at the tails, as both approach 0 at the lower end and 1 at the upper end.

A test statistic $T = n \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \{F_n(x) - F_0(x)\}^2 \psi(x) dF_0(x)$ based on the integral over the squared differences of the EDF $F_n(x)$ and the CDF $F_0(x)$ of $f_0(x)$ was developed by Cramér [88], von Mises [89] and Smirnov [90]. The differences are multiplied with a weighting function $\psi(x) \geq 0$ to give more importance to deviations in a certain region of x . Anderson and Darling proposed and studied the use of $\psi(x) = [F_0(x)\{1 - F_0(x)\}]^{-1}$, which is the reciprocal of the variance of the EDF under the null hypothesis [91], [92]. This weighting function diverges at the tails of the EDF, leading to the desired stronger weighting of deviations in this region. The Anderson-Darling test is one of the most powerful GOF tests in 1D, in particular it is usually more powerful than the frequently used Pearson's χ^2 test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test [93].

The two-sample extension of the Anderson-Darling test static is defined as

$$A_{nm}^2 = \frac{nm}{n+m} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\{F_n(x) - G_m(x)\}^2}{H_{n+m}(x)\{1 - H_{n+m}(x)\}} dH_{n+m}(x), \quad (4.7)$$

where $H_{n+m}(x) = \{nF_n(x) + mG_m(x)\}/n+m$ is the EDF of the pooled sample $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, \dots, c_{n+m})$ of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} [94], [95]. The integrand is defined to be zero for $H_{n+m}(x) = 1$, such that the integral exists. For a continuous population, the probability of a tie (i.e. two entries in \mathbf{c} being exactly the same) is zero. In this case, eq. (4.7) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} A_{nm}^2 &= \frac{nm}{n+m} \sum_{i=1}^{n+m-1} \frac{\left\{ \frac{M_i}{n} - \frac{i-M_i}{m} \right\}^2}{\frac{i}{n+m} \left\{ 1 - \frac{i}{n+m} \right\}} \\ &= \frac{1}{nm} \sum_{i=1}^{n+m-1} \frac{\{M_i(n+m) - ni\}^2}{i\{n+m-i\}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.8)$$

Figure 4.1: Illustration of the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. A toy data sample is compared to two reference models. In the left panels, the data and reference sample are drawn from the same distribution. In the right panels, the reference sample is drawn from a broader, shifted distribution. This can be seen in the normalized histograms shown in the upper panels. In the lower panels, the empirical distribution functions of both samples $F_n(x)$ and $G_m(x)$ are plotted. The maximal distance between $F_n(x)$ and $G_m(x)$ is the test statistic $D_{n,m}$, which is larger for the test with the incorrect model.

where M_i is the number of entries in \mathbf{a} that are less than or equal to the i -th smallest entry of the pooled sample \mathbf{c} .

In the *GOFevaluation* package, the generalized version of the test for two or more samples introduced in [96] and implemented in [97] is used. Here, eq. (4.8) is slightly modified to accommodate for ties that arise in nondegenerate samples. Additionally, in this implementation, the modified test statistic is subtracted by 1 and divided by the standard deviation of eq. (4.7).

Point-to-Point Test (Statistical Energy Test): This test assesses whether two samples $\mathbf{A} = (\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n)$ and $\mathbf{B} = (\mathbf{b}_1, \mathbf{b}_2, \dots, \mathbf{b}_m)$ of points \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{b}_i in d -dimensional phase space have the same underlying PDF. For our use-case, \mathbf{A} is a data sample and \mathbf{B} is a reference sample. The test statistic is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
T = & \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i,j>i}^n R(|\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_j|) \\
& + \frac{1}{m(m-1)} \sum_{i,j>i}^m R(|\mathbf{b}_i - \mathbf{b}_j|) \\
& - \frac{1}{nm} \sum_{i,j}^m R(|\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{b}_j|).
\end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

It is based on the weighted sums of all distances between points from \mathbf{A} (first term), all distances between points from \mathbf{B} (second term) and all distances between each point of \mathbf{A} and each point of \mathbf{B} (third term). $R(d)$ is an appropriate weighting function for a distance d . In the statistical literature, various functions are discussed [98]–[101] and implemented in the *GOFevaluation* package. For $R(d) = 1/d$, eq. (4.9) takes the form of the electrostatic energy of point charges with opposite signs at positions \mathbf{a}_i and \mathbf{b}_i , hence the naming of this test. The weighting functions are chosen such that less agreement results in larger T . In the picture of electrostatic energy, this corresponds to high potential energy due to a large distance between positive and negative charges compared to the distances between charges of the same sign. For the study discussed in section 4.4, $R(d) = -\log d$ is used.

In order to have negligible effects of statistical fluctuations of the reference sample one chooses $m \gg n$. In this case and with the approximation $n(n-1) \simeq n^2$, one can simplify eq. (4.9) to

$$T = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i,j>i}^n R(|\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{a}_j|) - \frac{1}{nm} \sum_{i,j}^m R(|\mathbf{a}_i - \mathbf{b}_j|). \tag{4.10}$$

Dropping the second term of eq. (4.9) shortens the processing time considerably and can be justified by the fact that the omitted term depends exclusively on the reference sample, which only results in a constant offset of T .

4.1.4 Estimation of the p-Value

If the PDF of the test statistic under the null hypothesis $g(T|H_0)$ is known, the p-value of a GOF test corresponding to the observed test statistic T_0 can be calculated analytically using eq. (4.1). For some GOF measures, analytical distributions are known. However, they are usually only approached asymptotically, i.e. for an infinite number of data points, and under certain conditions that are not always fulfilled. Therefore, in the *GOFevaluation* package, the p-value is calculated by estimating $g(T|H_0)$ empirically. Different methods are used for binned and unbinned GOF tests.

For binned GOF tests, the p-value estimation is illustrated in fig. 4.2. A number of n_{mc} binned toy data sets are Poisson sampled from the binned reference by drawing the number of counts in the i -th bin from a Poisson distribution with mean y_i . The test statistic T for each of these toy data sets and the binned reference is then calculated to obtain the empirical distribution of $g(T|H_0)$. The fraction of toy experiments in which the test statistics is below the observed value of the test statistic T_0 is then used as an estimate of the p-value.

Figure 4.2: **Left:** A normal distribution is fitted to binned data (red histogram). The bin-wise expectation values under the null hypothesis of the GOF test (blue dots) are used to generate n_{mc} binned toy data sets. The filled blue histogram shows one example of such a toy data set. **Right:** The test statistic T is calculated for each of the n_{mc} binned toy data sets. This yields the empirical distribution of the test statistic under the null hypothesis. The value of one minus the EDF of T at the observed value of the test statistic T_0 (solid red line) corresponds to the p-value of the GOF test (dotted red line).

For unbinned tests, the data sample of size N and the reference sample of size n_r are re-sampled from a pooled sample of size $N + n_r$. For this, the order of the pooled sample is randomized. Then, the first N entries are labeled *data* and the remaining n_r entries as *reference* and the test statistic for the two permuted samples is calculated. More details on this method can be found in appendix C of [85]. This is repeated

n_{perm} times to obtain the empirical distribution of $g(T|H_0)$. As for binned GOF tests, the fraction of toy experiments in which the test statistic T is smaller than the observed value T_0 is used to estimate the p-value of the GOF test.

4.2 Toy-Model Analysis

The performance of a GOF test can be studied by fitting incomplete models to toy data. Since there is no uniformly most powerful GOF test, it is crucial to study the power of various GOF tests on Monte Carlo data. A systematic study of the performance of GOF tests for a Dalitz-plot analysis is described in [85]. A similar study for the analysis of XENON recoil band data is presented in section 4.4. The same methods are also employed in section 4.3 to study the influence of the choice of the binning on the result of binned GOF tests. Hence, the underlying concepts of the toy-model analysis for XENON data are discussed in the following.

4.2.1 The XENON Electronic Recoil Model

For this study, a simplified version of the XENON1T SR1 electronic recoil (ER) model [75] in $cS1$ and $\log_{10} cS2$ is used. The generic shape is identical in XENONnT, and the results should moreover be valid in general for the analysis of recoil bands. The simplified model is characterized by three shape parameters, whose influence on the shape of the ER band is shown in fig. 4.3. For constant energy deposition, a larger photon yield (PY) causes the electron yield to decrease, which results in larger $cS1$ and smaller $cS2$ signals. Thus, the recoil band is shifted in $cS1$ - $\log_{10} cS2$ space to the lower right for larger values of PY (fig. 4.3 right). The recombination fluctuation (RF) quantifies the variation of the recombination fraction of initially separated electron-ion pairs. High values of RF broaden the recoil band, which is most visible at large values of $cS1$ (fig. 4.3 center). Both shape parameters are given in units of sigma deviation from the expectation of XENON1T SR1. While both PY and RF are parameters related to detector physics, the mismodeling fraction (MMF) proposed in [102] is introduced to account for signal-like shape-uncertainties in the ER model. A positive (negative) MMF adds (subtracts) a signal-like component to (from) the ER band (fig. 4.3 left). For a negative MMF, a region below the recoil band with vanishing expectation values occurs.

4.2.2 Rejection of Fits with Incomplete Models

The power of a GOF test can be evaluated using toy data. For this, toy data is generated from a PDF f and fitted with PDFs of incomplete models such that $f_0 \neq f$. Three incomplete ER models are obtained by fixing one of the shape parameters to zero. A GOF test with the *parent model* used to generate the toy data, as well as a GOF test with an *unconditional fit* with the complete model, are performed as

Figure 4.3: Impact of the three shape parameters on the electronic recoil (ER) band. The 0.5% and 99.5% quantiles, as well as the mean in $\log_{10} cS2$ for each bin in $cS1$, are shown for three different values of each parameter. A positive (negative) mismodeling fraction (MMF) adds (subtracts) a signal-like component to (from) the ER band. The recombination fluctuation (RF) broadens (positive value) or narrows (negative value) the recoil band and a variation of the photon yield (PY) causes a shift of the recoil band in the phase space.

cross-checks. The five PDFs considered in the toy-model analyses are summarized in table 4.1.

The parent model PDF is the only PDF that was not obtained by a fit. One expects a flat p-value distribution for any GOF test since H_0 is true by definition. In the following studies, two parent model are examined with the following non-zero shape parameters:

- *Parent Model 1:* $MMF = 0.03$, $PY = 0.8$, $RF = 1.5$
- *Parent Model 2:* $MMF = -0.03$, $PY = -0.8$, $RF = -1.5$.

For the unconditional fit, all parameters of the parent model are free parameters of the fit. Thus, the PDF is slightly different for each toy experiment. The p-value distribution for this fit is expected to be fairly flat with a slight bias toward large p-values since, on average, the unconditional fit agrees better with the data than the parent model.

The power of a GOF test is assessed by how well it rejects the three fits with incomplete models. To quantify this, n_{toy} toy experiments are performed. The *rejection power* is defined as the fraction of toy experiments in which the null hypothesis is rejected at C.L. $1 - \alpha$

Table 4.1: Overview of the five PDFs used in the toy-model analyses. The parent model has three shape parameters: mismodeling fraction (MMF), recombination fluctuation (RF), and photon yield (PY). All of them are free parameters for the unconditional fit. To study the performance to reject bad fits, three fits with incomplete models are performed. For each of them, one of the three shape parameters is fixed to 0.

PDF	Description
Parent model	PDF f that is used to generate all toy datasets
Unconditional fit	All parameters of the parent model are free parameters of the fit
Fit with fixed MMF	Same as the unconditional fit but with fixed MMF of 0
Fit with fixed RF	Same as the unconditional fit but with fixed RF of 0
Fit with fixed PY	Same as the unconditional fit but with fixed PY of 0

$$P_{\text{reject}}^{\alpha} = \frac{1}{n_{\text{toy}}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{toy}}} \mathbf{1}_{[0,\alpha)}(p_i) \quad (4.11)$$

with the p-value of the i -th toy experiment p_i and the indicator function $\mathbf{1}_A(x)$ of the subset A defined in eq. (4.6). For 90% confidence level (C.L.) this corresponds to the fraction of toy experiments in which the GOF test yields a p-value below 0.1. A sensitive GOF test will on average indicate a bad agreement of the fit model and data by a low p-value, thus resulting in a high rejection power. If the null hypothesis is true, one expects a flat p-value distribution. Thus, the rejection power at 90% C.L. is expected to be around 0.1, which corresponds to the expected statistical type I error.

All toy data from the simplified XENON1T SR1 ER model in this work was generated using proprietary software from the XENON collaboration. This software was also used to perform unbinned extended maximum likelihood fits of the various models to the toy data sets.

4.3 The Binning of Binned GOF Tests

The choice of the binning is a free parameter of binned GOF tests, which can affect the outcome of the test. It must therefore be given special attention. Technically, the simplest approach is to use regular binning with equally spaced partitions. However, as discussed below, GOF tests with regular binning are prone to errors. An alternative method is therefore discussed in the second part of this section. In this approach, irregular partitions are chosen such that the phase space is divided into regions with equal probability contents under the null hypothesis.

4.3.1 Regular Binning

For regularly binned data, the expectation values y_i of the fit PDF can range over multiple orders of magnitude. This is the case for the XENON ER data in cS1 and \log_{10} cS2. It features a high probability density around the median in cS2 and drops quickly for higher and lower cS2. These tails, however, are of particular interest since they have the largest overlap with the signal region. For binned GOF tests, an unreliable behavior was observed when the y_i contain expectation values below 1. In the following, only results for the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test are shown and discussed, but similar studies with equivalent results were also performed for the Pearson's χ^2 test.

Dependence of the Test Result on the Binning in XENON Toy Data

A toy-model analysis as discussed in section 4.2 was performed to study the influence of the granularity of the binning on the result of a GOF test. For this example, 100 toy data sets with an average size of 10 000 were generated from parent model 2 and fit with fixed MMF (see table 4.1). The original 12 348 bins of the binned reference with 98 partitions in cS1 and 126 in \log_{10} cS2 were merged to obtain coarser binnings with $k = 50 \times 64 = 3200$ and $k = 12 \times 15 = 80$ bins as shown in the upper panels of fig. 4.4. For each granularity, the p-values of the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test were obtained for each toy experiment. The results are shown in the lower panels of fig. 4.4. For the coarsest binning, most p-values are below 0.05, which is expected from the strong deviations of data and fit model below the recoil band. For the most granular binning, the p-values peak at 1, which leads to vanishing rejection power. If a two-sided GOF test is performed, i.e., if p-values below 0.05 and above 0.95 are rejected, part of the rejection power can be recovered. However, for the binning with intermediate granularity, the p-value distribution is essentially flat, which causes a complete loss of sensitivity of the test. Similar behavior was observed for other fits with incomplete models that overestimate the data in regions where the expected bin count rate is low. The distribution of the p-values heavily depends on the null hypothesis, therefore no unique optimal binning can be defined for regularly binned GOF tests. A binning that produces high rejection power for one incomplete model might yield a flat p-value distribution for another null hypothesis. Additionally, one has to consider that the power of the test decreases for too coarse binnings, as information encoded in the position of data points is lost.

Investigation of the Dependence of the Test Result on the Binning with Uniformly Distributed Toy Data

The effect of p-values close to one for granularly binned GOF tests was reproduced with uniformly distributed toy data. This allowed studying the effect of low expectation values isolated from other effects. A uniform distribution with $N_0 \gg N$ was chosen as a null hypothesis for the GOF test. This represents a particularly bad fit that overestimates the data.

Figure 4.4: Illustration of the influence of the number of bins k on the result of a binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test. In the upper panels, the expected number of counts in each bin y_i for one fit with an incomplete model is shown for varying granularity of the binning. The corresponding toy data sample is overlaid for reference. The bottom panels show the corresponding p-values of 100 toy experiments. For the least granular binning, most p-values are below 0.1, as expected for a poor fit. For the finest binning, no p-values below 0.1 are observed. Instead, the distribution peaks at 1. For a binning with intermediate granularity, the p-value distribution is nearly flat.

$N = 400$ toy data points were drawn from a uniform distribution, while $N_0 = 500$ uniformly distributed events were expected under the null hypothesis. The data was binned with $k = 10$, $k = 500$, and $k = 5000$ bins. This means that the constant expectation values in each bin $y = y_i = N_0/k \forall i$ vary between $y = 50$ and $y = 0.01$. For each binning, 100 toy experiments were performed and the results of the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test were calculated with the *GOFevaluation* package. Figure 4.5 shows the binned data and expectation values (first row) as well as the distribution of p-values (second row) for the three granularities of the binning. One observes a similar behavior as seen with the ER toy data in fig. 4.4. For coarse binning (large y), the p-values peak at zero, as one would expect. For $y = 1$, however, the p-value distribution becomes flat and for even lower y , the p-values peak at 1.

To understand the origin of this behavior, the empirical distribution of the test statistic $g(T|H_0)$ was studied in more detail. As discussed in section 4.1.4, this distribution is obtained using binned toy data which is Poisson sampled from the expected values under H_0 . For uniformly distributed data, each value of T only depends on the total number of counts of the binned toy N^* and the distribution of the N^* events among the k bins. The number of counts in the i -th bin n_i^* is Poisson

distributed with mean y . Therefore, $N^* = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i^*$ is Poisson distributed with mean $N_0 = \sum_{i=1}^k y_i = ky$. The partial empirical distributions of $g(T|H_0)$ for six values of N^* are shown in fig. 4.5 (third row) for the three binnings. The observed value of the test statistic T_0 of a data set with $N = 400$ events will follow the distribution of a fixed $N^* = N = 400$, which is shown in gray in the plot.

For large y , T is on average larger for any $N^* \neq N_0$ compared to the distribution for $N^* = N_0$ (fig. 4.5 third row left). The individual distributions only depend on the absolute value of the deviation of N^* from N_0 . Thus, it is degenerate concerning the sign of the deviation and, on average, any departure from N_0 leads to a low p-value. For very low y , this degeneracy is suspended (fig. 4.5 third row right). The partial distributions of $g(T|H_0)$ are distinct for each value of N^* and ordered by N^* . In this case, if the fit strongly overestimates the data, i.e., if $N_0 \gg N$, the test statistic T_0 is at the very low end of $g(T|H_0)$, which gives rise to p-values close to 1. For intermediate expectation values, the distribution of the test statistic is independent of N^* (fig. 4.5 third row center), which gives rise to the corresponding flat p-value distribution.

To understand the ordering of partial distributions of $g(T|H_0)$ by N^* for small y , their combinatorial composition was examined. For large y , the Poisson distribution for the number of counts in the i -th bin n_i^* is broad and multiple combinations of n_i^* have a sufficiently high probability to be relevant for $g(T|H_0)$. For very low y , in turn, the Poisson distribution of the n_i^* peaks at zero, and the probability to find more than one count per bin becomes small. For $y = 0.01$, the average number of bins with two counts in one bin is only about $5 \times 10^{-5}k$. The combinatorial composition of the partial distribution $g(T|H_0)$ for fixed $N^* = N_0 = 500$ is illustrated in fig. 4.6 for $y = 0.01$ (top) and $y = 0.001$ (bottom). The Poisson likelihood χ^2 was calculated for 10 000 toy experiments. The total distributions consist of the discrete value obtained for 500 times one count per bin (red bin), the distribution of at least one bin with two counts but no bin with more than two counts (blue bins), and the distribution of at least one bin with three counts but no bin with more than three counts (green bins). For $y = 0.01$, even two toy data sets with four counts in one bin are observed (white bins). For smaller y , the distribution becomes narrower with a maximum at the value of N^* bins containing one count and all other $k - N^*$ bins containing no counts. In the limit of binary bin counts for $y = \frac{N_0}{k} \ll 1$, eq. (4.2) can be approximated by $\chi_{\text{P}}^2 \simeq N^* \frac{(1-y)^2}{y} + (k - N^*)y = N^* \left(\frac{k}{N_0} - 2 \right) + N_0$, which is linear in N^* . Similarly, for eq. (4.4), one obtains the linear approximation $\chi_{\lambda}^2 \simeq 2N_0 + 2N^*(\ln(k/N_0) - 1)$.

To summarize, for small y , the small number of sufficiently probable combinations to distribute N^* events among k bins makes T a simple function that is linear in N^* . This explains the large p-values observed for fits if they overestimate the data in a region with small expected values.

Another problem that arises with low binwise expectation values $y = N_0/k$ is that the mean and/or variance of $g(T|H_0)$ depend on y . For the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test statistic, both approach zero for small y and for Pearson's χ^2 , the variance diverges. A detailed discussion including calculations of the asymptotic expressions can be

Figure 4.5: A binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test was performed for uniformly distributed toy data sets of size $N = 400$ and a uniform reference with a total number of expected events $N_0 = 500$. In the three columns, only the granularity of the binning is altered by varying the number of bins k . The panels in the top row show an example of binned toy data and the expected value in each bin. The p-values of 100 toy experiments are shown in the second row. For coarse binning, the p-values strongly peak at zero, as expected for a poor fit. For the most granular binning, in turn, the distribution peaks at one. For an intermediate binning, the p-value distribution becomes nearly flat. To explain this behavior, the bottom panels show the part of the test statistic distribution under the null hypothesis (colored histograms) modeled by Poisson sampling for a selection of fixed values $N^* = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i^*$ of the Poisson sampled binned toy data with n_i^* counts in the i -th bin. The distribution of T for $N^* = N = 400$ is shown for reference in gray.

Figure 4.6: The distribution of the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test statistic T obtained from toy data is shown for a granular binning such that the number of expected events in each bin is $y = 0.01$. For a fixed number of toy data points $N^* = N_0 = 500$, the value of T only depends on the combinatorial possibilities to distribute N^* events among k bins. For low y , only a few combinations yield sufficiently large probabilities so that the distribution becomes narrow.

found in [103]. The according values obtained from toy simulations are shown in appendix A. Even though we do not want to use the asymptotic behavior of the test statistic, this has implications on binned GOF tests in which the fit PDF features various y . According to [103], the non-constant mean of the Poisson likelihood χ^2 can lead to a loss of sensitivity for statistically significant deviations in bins with low y . For Pearson's χ^2 , due to the diverging variance for low y , statistical fluctuations in these bins can hide bad disagreement in the rest of the bins.

4.3.2 Equiprobable Binning

As demonstrated above, unreliable behavior can occur in GOF tests with regular binnings. In particular, when expectation values y_i below 1 occur, such behavior is observed. This can be overcome by using an irregular binning, which is defined such that the expected value in each bin is the same. Using such a binning for χ^2 GOF tests was first suggested by Mann and Wald [104]. In their study, the authors derived a formula for the optimal number of equiprobable bins, which depends on the total number of data points N , and the confidence level of the test. This was intended to resolve the ambiguity of one-dimensional binned GOF tests resulting from the choice of binning. For higher-dimensional data, some ambiguity in the GOF test cannot be avoided even with equiprobable binning, as we will see later. Nevertheless, the use of equiprobable binning is well suited to obtain sensitive binned GOF tests without the unreliable behavior observed in regularly binned tests. In the following, an algorithm to define an equiprobable binning is presented, and optimal binning parameters for the XENON ER band model are investigated.

Equiprobable Binning Algorithm

A simple algorithm to divide the d -dimensional phase space of a fit PDF $f_0(x)$ into k equiprobable bins based on the quantiles of $f_0(x)$ is described in [83]. For $d = 1$ dimension, the codomain $[0, 1]$ of the CDF $F_0(x)$ of $f_0(x)$ is divided into k equal parts. The intersections of each boundary with $F_0(x)$ then yield the bin edges of the equiprobable binning, as illustrated in fig. 4.7. In practice, the bin edges are computed based on a reference sample of size n_r drawn from f_0 . The size of this reference sample is chosen to be much larger than the size of the data sample N so that statistical fluctuations in the reference sample are negligible. In the following, $n_r = 100 N$ is used.

For $d > 1$ dimensions, the fit PDF is a function of $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d)$. The phase space is divided into $k = \prod_i^d k_i$ equiprobable bins, where the number of partitions in the i -th dimension is k_i . The bin edges are defined in a nested way, as illustrated in fig. 4.8 for $d = 2$. One starts by defining k_1 equiprobable bins based on $F_0(x_1)$ analogue to the 1D case (see fig. 4.8 a with $k_1 = 5$). Then, for each bin in x_1 , k_2 equiprobable bins in x_2 are defined (see fig. 4.8 b with $k_2 = 5$). For $d > 2$, one proceeds in this fashion for all d dimensions. For each of the so defined bins, the number of data points inside is determined (see fig. 4.8 c). The GOF test now reduces to testing whether the data is uniformly distributed among the bins with an expected value N_0/k in each bin. The color scheme of the equiprobable binning can be chosen such that regions in which the fit underestimates (overestimates) the data are red (blue), as shown in fig. 4.8 d. In this way, regions with large deviations from uniformity can be easily identified. As an example, the equiprobably binned data for the five PDFs defined in table 4.1 are shown in fig. B.1 for parent model 1 and fig. B.2 for parent model 2 in the appendices.

In one dimension, the introduced algorithm provides a unique way to partition the

Figure 4.7: Illustration of the equiprobable binning algorithm in 1D. The codomain of the cumulative distribution function $F_0(x)$ is divided into 10 equidistant sections by the gray dotted lines. The intersection of each of the lines with $F_0(x)$ (blue line) defines the location of bin edges in x (red vertical lines). The density of the reference sample used to define the equiprobable binning is visualized below.

phase space into k bins. For $d > 1$ dimensions, this is no longer the case: The choice of the number of partitions in each dimension k_i , as well as the order in which the partitioning is performed, are free parameters. One can, however, take advantage of these additional degrees of freedom by choosing them in a way that best suits the problem. For instance, if a certain parameter is particularly sensitive to the tested hypothesis, the binning can be chosen more granularly in that dimension. An implementation of the algorithm in 1D and 2D is available in the *GOFevaluation* package [78].

Optimal Binning Parameters

As mentioned above, a formula for the optimal choice of the number of bins k_{opt} was developed in [104]. At 90% C.L. the formula for N data points is $k_{\text{opt}} = 4.163(N - 1)^{2/5}$ for $N \geq 200$. A generalized formula

$$k_{\text{opt}} = b \left[\frac{\sqrt{2}(N - 1)}{\lambda_\alpha + \lambda_{1-p_0}} \right]^{2/5}, \quad (4.12)$$

was derived in [83]. Here, p_0 is the lower bound of the power level of the test, $1 - \alpha$ is the confidence level of the test, λ_c is the value that fulfills $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{\lambda_c}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}} dx$, and b is a constant between 2 and 4. For $b = 4$ and $p_0 = 1/2$, one obtains the formula

Figure 4.8: Illustration of how 25 equiprobable bins can be defined in 2D and how data is binned accordingly. The binning is defined on a reference sample (blue dots, here $n_r = 1250 = 10 N$ for illustration purposes). **a:** First, 5 equiprobable bins are defined in x_1 . **b:** In a second step, 5 equiprobable bins are defined in x_2 for each partition in x_1 . The so defined binning has exactly 50 reference samples in each bin. **c:** The data sample (red dots) is binned with the previously defined equiprobable binning. **d:** Resulting 2D equiprobable histogram of the data sample.

developed by Mann and Wald. In [105], it was suggested to halve the number of bins for practical purposes, which corresponds to a choice of $b = 2$.

In d dimensions, besides the total number of bins $k = \prod_{i=1}^d k_i$, the number of bins in each dimension k_i and the order in which to apply the algorithm can be optimized. To assess how the choice of k and the individual k_i influence the power of GOF tests for our practical application of ER band fit in cS1 and \log_{10} cS2, a toy-model analysis as discussed in section 4.2 was performed. The number of bins k_i in the two dimensions are referred to as k_{cS1} and $k_{\log \text{cS2}}$, respectively. Figure 4.9 shows the rejection power at 90% C.L. of the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test for different equiprobable binnings. The results for the fit with fixed MMF (left) and the fit with fixed PY (right) as introduced in table 4.1 are shown. For each data point, 100 toy

Figure 4.9: Rejection power of the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test for two fits with incomplete models as a function of the total number of equiprobable bins k . For each color, the number of partitions in cS1 is constant. For the equiprobable binning, first cS1 then \log_{10} cS2 is partitioned. The optimal values k_{opt} for $b \in \{2, 3, 4\}$ are shown for reference. Additionally, the rejection power expected for the true null hypothesis 0.1 is indicated by a horizontal line.

experiments, each with a toy data set with $N = 1000$ events, were performed. For this study, first cS1 and then \log_{10} cS2 were partitioned.

One can see that the highest rejection power is achieved with a total number of bins close to the one provided by eq. (4.12) for $p_0 = 0.5$ ($\lambda_{1-p_0} = 0$), $\alpha = 0.9$ ($\lambda_\alpha = 1.28$), and $b \in [2, 4]$. For the same total number of bins k , different combinations of k_{cS1} and $k_{\log \text{cS2}}$ yield different rejection powers. For the toy experiments discussed here, the optimal number of partitions in cS1 seems to be around 4. Fixing $k_{\text{cS1}} = 4$, the maximum rejection power is reached for $k > k_{\text{opt}}(b = 4)$ for the fit with fixed MMF and for $k < k_{\text{opt}}(b = 2)$ for the fit with fixed PY. This confirms the findings in [106] that the optimal number of bins depends on the distribution to be tested. The variation of the rejection power for $k_{\text{opt}}(b = 2) < k < k_{\text{opt}}(b = 4)$ is about 25%. For $k_{\text{cS1}} = 4$, the highest rejection power for both fits with incomplete models is achieved between $k = 16$ and $k = 80$, which corresponds to $k_{\log \text{cS2}}$ between 2 and 20. Both mismodelings are most apparent in \log_{10} cS2, thus it is not surprising that a high rejection power is obtained for $k_{\log \text{cS2}} > k_{\text{cS1}}$.

The same study was performed with inverse binning order, for which the overall rejection power of the test slightly decreased. This might be due to geometrical effects as the distribution of the recoil band is flat in cS1 in first order and varies in \log_{10} cS2. Similar results were observed with Pearson's χ^2 test.

Evidently, there is no unique binning that gives the highest power for any equiprobably binned GOF test, as the optimal choice of parameters depends on f_0 . However, if one chooses the k_{cS1} and $k_{\log \text{cS2}}$ for $b \in [2, 4]$, the observed variation of the rejection power is acceptably low, so the exact choice of the binning does not strongly influence the outcome of the test. From the toy-model analyses one can derive the following recommendations for choosing the parameters for an equiprobable binning:

1. Calculate the optimal total number of bins k_{opt} using eq. (4.12) with $b = 3$.
2. Find integer numbers k_i that are close to the calculated optimal number of bins when multiplied $k = \prod_{i=1}^d k_i \simeq k_{\text{opt}}$.
3. If one of the parameters is more sensitive to the tested hypothesis, more bins in this dimension should be chosen, e.g. $k_{\log_{10} \text{cS2}} > k_{\text{cS1}}$.

4.4 GOF Tests for XENONnT Data Analysis

In the following, a systematic study is discussed to search for GOF tests that are well suited to identify fits with incomplete models in the context of XENONnT data analysis. For this, a toy-model analysis with the three incomplete ER models introduced in table 4.1 was performed.

4.4.1 Setup of the Study

The power to reject the three fits with incomplete models was evaluated for a selection of GOF tests and three different mean toy data sizes $\bar{N} = 100$, $\bar{N} = 1000$ and $\bar{N} = 10000$. The number of data points N in $\text{cS1-log}_{10} \text{cS2}$ space in one toy data set was Poisson sampled from the respective mean value. The five GOF tests introduced in section 4.1.2 and section 4.1.3 were performed. Both regularly binned and equiprobably binned data were used for the two χ^2 GOF tests. The binning parameters of the equiprobable binnings are summarized in table 4.2. They were obtained following the recommendations provided in section 4.3.2. For all binnings, first cS1 then $\log_{10} \text{cS2}$ was binned. For the regularly binned tests, 98 bins in cS1 from 3 PE to 100 PE and 126 bins in $\log_{10} \text{cS2}$ from 1.7 to 3.9 were chosen. For each toy experiment, n_r reference samples were drawn from each of the PDFs introduced in table 4.1 to perform the unbinned GOF methods as well as the equiprobably binned GOF tests. A value $n_r = 100\bar{N}$ was chosen so that the statistical fluctuations of the reference samples could be neglected. The two unbinned 1D GOF tests were performed only in $\log_{10} \text{cS2}$ since this component is most sensitive to the mismodelings. The entire study was conducted twice, with the two parent models introduced in section 4.2.2 that have different non-zero shape parameters. For each configuration of the data sample size \bar{N} and each of the two parent models, $n_{\text{toy}} = 100$ toy experiments were performed to obtain the distributions of p-values and rejection powers of the GOF tests.

Due to the huge computation time of the Point-to-point GOF test, only $n_{\text{perm}} = 100$ permutations were performed for the p-value estimation. For a fair comparison between all GOF tests, $n_{\text{mc}} = n_{\text{perm}} = 100$ was chosen for all tests.

Table 4.2: Optimal number of bins k_{opt} computed with eq. (4.12) with $b = 3$ for the three toy sample sizes \bar{N} . The number of partitions in cS1 k_{cS1} and the number of partitions in \log_{10} cS2 $k_{\log_{\text{cS2}}}$ are chosen such that the total number of bins $k = k_{\text{cS1}}k_{\log_{\text{cS2}}}$ is close to k_{opt} . For reference, the number of expected events in each bin is provided in the last column.

\bar{N}	k_{opt}	k_{cS1}	$k_{\log_{\text{cS2}}}$	k	\bar{N}/k
100	19.6	2	9	18	5.6
1000	49.5	4	12	48	20.8
10 000	124.3	6	19	114	87.7

4.4.2 Results of the Performance Study

Rejection Power

In total, $n_{\text{toy}} = 100$ toy datasets were generated for each of the **3** data sample sizes \bar{N} and the **2** parent models. For each toy dataset, **4** fits were performed. For each fit and **1** sample from the parent model, **(5+2)** GOF tests were performed. This resulted in a total of $100 \times 3 \times 2 \times (4+1) \times (5+2) = 2100$ p-values to examine². The distribution of p-values for parent model 2 is shown for the equiprobably binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test in fig. 4.10a. One can see that for the parent model, the distribution is flat within statistical uncertainties regardless of \bar{N} . This is an important check for the validity of the study. For the unconditional fit, a slight bias towards larger p-values can be seen as expected. For the three fits with incomplete models, the distribution is rather flat for $\bar{N} = 100$, but for larger \bar{N} , most GOF tests yield a p-value below 0.1.

For the regularly binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test shown in fig. 4.10b, one can see that the fit with fixed MMF and the fit with fixed RF leads to high p-values for data from parent model 2 (low p-values for parent model 1). Moreover, the p-values of all fits with $\bar{N} = 100$ are distributed between 0.2 and 0.8 with a maximum at around 0.5. In parent model 2, the negative MMF and RF lead to an overestimation of the data by the fit in a region of low expectation values. The occurrence of large p-values, in this case, was studied and discussed in section 4.3.1. For the fit with fixed PY, the effect is not present, possibly since this mismodeling only causes a shift of the ER band fit relative to the data, resulting in simultaneous under- and overestimation in regions with low expected values.

To compare the performances of the 5+2 GOF tests, the rejection power at 90% C.L. as defined in eq. (4.11) was calculated for each model and each GOF test. To account for potential high p-values of a bad fit, a two-sided test was performed for

²Actually, for the Point-to-point GOF test, $N = 10\,000$ was excluded, so the number should be reduced by 300.

all regularly binned GOF tests. Here, H_0 was rejected for p-values below 0.05 or above 0.95. For the Point-to-point test, only $\bar{N} = 100$ and $\bar{N} = 1000$ were tested because of its long processing time. For parent model 2, Pearson's χ^2 test could not be calculated due to bins with expectation values of zero that arise with a negative MMF. These would cause an infinite test statistic. The rejection power is shown as a function of \bar{N} in fig. 4.11a for parent model 1 and fig. 4.11b for parent model 2. The validity of the study can be verified based on the result of the tests for the parent model and unconditional fit. For the parent model, a rejection power around 0.1 is observed for all tests. For parent model 1, most rejection powers are slightly above the expected value. More statistics would be needed to verify whether this trend persists. For the unconditional fits, the rejection power is on average slightly lower than 0.1, as expected.

For the three fits with incomplete models, a rejection power above 0.1 indicates an effective rejection of the incorrect null hypothesis. For most tests, the rejection power for both parent models are similar for the fit with fixed PY and the fit with fixed RF. For the fit with fixed MMF, a higher rejection power is achieved for the parent model with positive MMF compared to the one with negative MMF. This can be understood from the definition of the MMF parameter. It affects the shape in a non-linear way, which can be seen in fig. 4.3. For the fit with fixed MMF, regularly binned GOF tests perform well in most cases – in particular Pearson's χ^2 test. However, the performance for the fit with fixed RF and the fit with fixed PY is poor. This is most striking for $\bar{N} = 10000$ and parent model 1. While all other test have a rejection power of 1, Pearson's χ^2 test is at almost 0. Similarly, the regularly binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test shows a particularly low rejection power compared to the other tests for the fit with fixed PY for $\bar{N} < 10000$. Moreover, the non-flat p-value distribution of the regularly binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test for $\bar{N} = 100$ leads to a rejection power of zero or close to zero for all fits.

The equiprobably binned GOF tests show similar rejection powers compared to the unbinned tests. For the fit with fixed RF and $\bar{N} = 10000$, the equiprobably binned tests perform best. Among the unbinned GOF tests, the Anderson-Darling test performs best in most cases. The performance of the Point-to-point test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test are comparable.

Processing Time

The processing time will not be the deciding criterion in the choice of a GOF test for high-level analyses, since it can generally be circumvented by parallelization. Still, it is interesting to study the time required to perform a single GOF test. Figure 4.12 shows the processing time to perform one GOF test as a function of \bar{N} . The processing time is highest for the Point-to-point test and increases approximately quadratically with \bar{N} . For the regularly binned GOF tests, the processing time is constant. Here, the binning has already been applied before performing the GOF test. For the other four tests, the processing time increases linearly with \bar{N} .

(a) p-value distribution for an equiprobably binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test.

(b) p-value distribution for a regularly binned Poisson likelihood χ^2 test.

Figure 4.10: The toy data sample with average size \bar{N} is drawn from parent model 2 with mismodelling fraction $\text{MMF} = -0.03$, photon yield $\text{PY} = -0.8$, and recombination fluctuation $\text{RF} = -1.5$. The five panels of each plot show the p-value distributions of the five PDFs defined in table 4.1.

(a) Rejection power for parent model 1 with mismodelling fraction $\text{MMF} = 0.03$, photon yield $\text{PY} = 0.8$, and recombination fluctuation $\text{RF} = 1.5$.

(b) Rejection power for parent model 2 with $\text{MMF} = -0.03$, $\text{PY} = -0.8$, and $\text{RF} = -1.5$

Figure 4.11: Rejection power as a function of the average size of the toy data sample \bar{N} for seven GOF tests. The five panels of each plot show the rejection power of each test for the five PDFs defined in table 4.1. The solid yellow and magenta lines correspond to the χ^2 tests with equiprobable binning.

Figure 4.12: Processing time for one GOF test as a function of the average size of the toy data sample \bar{N} . The solid yellow and magenta lines correspond to the χ^2 tests with equiprobable binning.

4.5 Summary of GOF Studies for the Analysis of XENONnT

Within the context of this work, the *GOFevaluation* software package was developed with the aim to streamline GOF testing. The package offers the possibility to perform various binned and unbinned GOF tests without relying on any asymptotic behavior of the test statistic. It is publicly available and widely used by analysts in the XENON collaboration.

Using this software, various toy model analyses were performed to select well-suited GOF tests for the analysis of recoil bands in XENON. For this, the effect of the choice of bins for binned GOF tests was studied first. An unreliable behavior for regularly binned GOF tests was observed and investigated. The studies presented above demonstrate that the result of a regularly binned GOF test strongly depend on the granularity of the binning. In several cases, this led to a complete loss of power of the tests. Since we do not know what kind of mismodeling might occur in a real experiment (otherwise we would of course include it in our model), this loss of sensitivity diminishes the usefulness of regularly binned GOF tests. To avoid such behavior, an irregular binning algorithm with equal expected values in each bin was discussed, and optimal binning parameters for the analyses of the XENON ER band were investigated. Recommendations for the choice of parameters are provided.

A comprehensive toy model analysis was performed with all GOF tests implemented in the *GOFevaluation* package. Among the tested GOF measures, the Anderson-Darling test, as well as the two equiprobably binned χ^2 -tests, were shown to be best suited to reject fits with incomplete models of the ER band in XENON analyses. The

good performance of 1D unbinned tests can be attributed to the fact that all three fits with incomplete models are most apparent in only one of the two dimensions (cS2). However, one could think of a mismodeling that is not detectable at all in only one of the dimensions. Therefore, GOF tests with lower dimensionality than the fit should only be used as a supplement. The two equiprobably binned GOF tests showed comparable performance throughout the study. Although in some cases regularly binned GOF tests perform better than equiprobably binned GOF tests, the observed shortcomings of regularly binned tests outweigh this advantage. Dedicated outlier detection methods might be well suited to achieve similar sensitivity in the cases in which the regularly binned tests perform well. Other studies suggested that the power of binned GOF tests can be increased substantially by choosing irregular but non-equiprobable bins [106], [107]. With this approach, it might be possible to combine the best of both worlds. In future studies, it would also be interesting to further explore the plentitude of d-dimensional unbinned GOF tests. Such tests with similar (or better) performance than the tests considered in this study would be crucial for multivariate analyses.

5 Towards an Automated Krypton Assay in Xenon

As discussed in section 2.5, the β^- -decay of ^{85}Kr will be one of the main internal backgrounds in XENONnT. It is possible to reduce the concentration of krypton in xenon from around ppb-level in commercially available gas to below 100 ppq by means of cryogenic krypton distillation [44] as motivated in section 2.1. To verify such an ultra-low contamination and to model the background contribution of the remaining ^{85}Kr , it is important to precisely quantify the concentration of krypton in the target material. For this purpose, the rare gas mass spectrometer (RGMS) operated at MPIK Heidelberg measures the krypton concentration of regularly extracted samples from XENONnT. In the first step, the traces of krypton in a sample are separated from the bulk of xenon by a gas chromatography system. Then, the amount of krypton is measured using a sensitive mass spectrometer. A fully automated rare gas mass spectrometer (Auto-RGMS) is envisaged for the krypton assay of future low-background LXe detectors. In the context of this work, a prototype of the automated gas chromatography system of Auto-RGMS was built and operated.

The difficulties of measuring ultra-low concentrations of krypton in xenon are outlined below, followed by a brief discussion of the operating principle of RGMS and the design of Auto-RGMS. Then, a brief introduction to concepts of gas chromatography relevant to this work is given. Thereafter, the prototype of the developed automated gas chromatography setup is introduced and the various measurements performed with it are described.

5.1 Krypton Assay in Xenon

As motivated above, the determination of the concentration of ^{85}Kr in xenon is an important input for a robust background model for any low-background LXe detector. For the ultra-low krypton in xenon concentration below 100 ppq, which is aimed in XENONnT [15], and the abundance of $^{85}\text{Kr} / ^{\text{nat}}\text{Kr} = 2 \times 10^{-11}$ mol/mol [70], a sensitivity to concentrations as low as 10^{-24} mol/mol would be required to directly measure the fraction of ^{85}Kr present in the xenon target.

With atom trap trace analysis (ATTA) it is possible to achieve a sensitivity to single ^{85}Kr atoms. The most sensitive measurement so far achieved a detection level of 10^{-17} mol/mol of atmospheric ^{85}Kr in air samples [108], which is not sufficient for the krypton assay in LXe detectors. Therefore, the concentration of ^{85}Kr in xenon is instead determined indirectly by measuring the more abundant stable isotopes ^{84}Kr and ^{86}Kr and inferring the contamination by ^{85}Kr from this measurement based on

its known isotopic abundance. This relaxes the demand of sensitivity to detecting a contamination of 100 ppq, which is, however, still very ambitious. An ATTA system with expected krypton in xenon sensitivity at the ppt level was discussed in [109]. Another approach for the indirect quantification of the ^{85}Kr contamination in xenon is based on the separation of krypton and xenon via gas chromatography and the subsequent counting of krypton ions in a mass spectrometer. The rare gas mass spectrometer (RGMS) operated at MPIK Heidelberg is the most sensitive detector for such a measurement [110].

5.1.1 The Rare Gas Mass Spectrometer at MPIK

The RGMS has already been used to measure the contamination of ^{85}Kr in the target of XENON100 and XENON1T [110], [111]. Due to its outstanding sensitivity, it is still used to monitor the krypton concentration of XENONnT. In this apparatus, the amount of krypton is quantified with a mass spectrometer, which is capable of detecting an amount of krypton below $10^{-13}\text{cm}^3\text{STP}^1$ [112]. This means that to measure a concentration of 100 ppq krypton in xenon, a sample of about $1\text{cm}^3\text{STP}$ is required. However, for accurate measurement of the mass spectrometer, a sufficiently large mean free path of the ions must be ensured, which requires a residual pressure in the system below 10^{-6}mbar [113]. For this reason, the traces of krypton are separated from the bulk of xenon using a gas chromatography system before being quantified by the mass spectrometer.

Figure 5.1 shows a simplified sketch of the setup. A sample of the target material extracted from XENONnT is stored in a stainless steel sample pipette, which is connected to the RGMS (“Xe batch in”). A fraction of the sample is expanded into a calibration volume V_{cal} , where the size of the batch is determined by measuring the pressure P . The batch is then frozen at LN_2 temperature onto a column filled with an adsorbent (T2). To start the separation process, the temperature of the column is increased and it is flushed with ultra-pure helium. The increase in temperature is achieved by immersing T2 in a cooling bath with a fixed initial temperature of -90°C . The helium is purified by an upstream adsorption column (T1) before flushing through T2. This column is also filled with an adsorbent and is constantly kept at the temperature of LN_2 to effectively trap trace amounts of krypton to achieve a krypton concentration in helium below the ppq level [114].

Due to its greater adsorption force, xenon propagates more slowly through the column compared to krypton, resulting in the separation of the two gases. More details on the principles of adsorption used for gas chromatography are provided in section 5.2. The krypton eluting from T2 is collected in the downstream column T3, which is built identical to T2 and kept at the temperature of LN_2 . A valve connecting T2 and T3 is closed as soon as all the krypton in T3 has eluted after around 18 minutes. At this point, no xenon elutes for about another 100 minutes [114], so the two components are separated. After the remaining helium is pumped from T3, the

¹ $1\text{cm}^3\text{STP}$ corresponds to a volume of 1cm^3 at a temperature of 0°C and a pressure of 100kPa

Figure 5.1: Simplified schematic drawing of the RGMS setup. In the gas chromatography system, krypton is separated from the bulk of xenon in adsorption column T2 and collected in adsorption column T3. The amount of krypton is then determined by the mass spectrometer. For this, the gas is ionized, accelerated, and deflected based on the mass-over-charge ratio of each ion. A secondary electron multiplier (SEM) detects the rate of ions at a fixed angle. More details about the workflow are given in the text.

column is heated to release the adsorbed krypton. It is then transferred to a cold finger by cryogenic pumping.

After 40 min, the cold finger is warmed to ambient temperature and the amounts of ^{84}Kr and ^{86}Kr are measured by the mass spectrometer. First, the gas released from the cold finger is ionized, focused, and accelerated in the ion source. The trajectories of different ions are deflected in a magnetic dipole field depending on their mass-to-charge ratios. The rate of ions at a fixed angle is measured by a secondary electron multiplier (SEM). The isotope measured by the SEM can be selected by adjusting the magnetic field strength. In addition to the rates of ^{84}Kr and ^{86}Kr , which are required to determine the amount of krypton of the batch, ^{36}Ar is measured. Moreover, at the end of a measurement, the rate of double ionized ^{130}Xe is quantified to verify the efficiency of the chromatographic separation.

A *blank measurement* is regularly performed to evaluate the background contamination of krypton that does not originate from the sample. For this, the same measurement procedure is used as for a regular sample measurement, with the only difference that no sample is injected. The obtained background rate is then subtracted from a sample measurement. Between two sample measurements, the entire system is baked out and pumped and the columns are heated and flushed with helium to remove residual gas.

The detection limit of RGMS under optimal conditions is 8 ppq [110], but, in practice, it is often at the order of a few 10 ppq due to the memory mentioned in section 5.1.2 and aging of the SEM.

5.1.2 From RGMS to Auto-RGMS

For future low-background LXe detectors such as DARWIN, a $^{\text{nat}}\text{Kr}/\text{Xe}$ concentration of 30 ppq is targeted [115]. The detection limit achieved with RGMS in practice is thus not sufficient to reliably measure the aimed krypton concentration with small errors. In addition, the system is operated fully manually, which introduces systematic uncertainties. Finally, after a measurement, a long bake-out time of one day is needed to recover the required low blank rate. It would be desirable to increase the frequency in which samples can be measured to characterize and model time-dependent variations of the krypton concentration in the detector. To meet all these requirements, a new, fully automated system with increased sensitivity is being developed and built at MPIK – the Auto-RGMS. Automation includes automatic control of helium flow, pressure, and temperature of the three columns and the cold finger. In addition, all valves will be electronically controllable so that the entire sequence for a measurement can be programmed.

The fully automated operation will reduce systematic uncertainties compared to the RGMS due to better parameter control. The more robust separation will allow the injection of larger batch sizes into the gas chromatography system, which will improve the detection limit. To avoid premature xenon breakthrough times due to column saturation at larger batch sizes, larger adsorption columns will be used for Auto-RGMS. This is expected to additionally increase the resolution of the separation, which is proportional to the square root of the column length [116]. Further performance improvements are anticipated by replacing the adsorbent *Chromosorb 102* by Johns Manville used in the columns T2 and T3 of the RGMS with a more suitable material for Auto-RGMS. *Chromosorb 102* is a porous organic polymer with an average pore size of about 85 Å and it is heatable only up to about 170 °C before it disintegrates. This results in the need for the long bake-out time of one day to remove the remaining gas from columns T2 and T3. The occurrence of a high blank measurement directly after a measurement is referred to as *memory effect*. In addition, the separation of krypton and xenon achieved with *Chromosorb 102* is not optimal and it constantly outgasses organic contaminants into the system. A higher separation power would allow to further increase the batch size and thus lower the detection limit. A reduced memory effect would shorten the time required for a measurement and thus allow a higher sample throughput. In a previous work, several new adsorbents were investigated with the aim of achieving both objectives [117]. A selection of activated carbons showed very promising separation resolutions meet these criteria to a high degree and exhibit much higher separation. Moreover, the higher maximal temperatures between 300 °C and 450 °C of the tested adsorbents could lead to a reduction of the memory effect compared to *Chromosorb 102*. Another feature of Auto-RGMS will be a system that allows the parallel operation of two sample pipettes. This way the overall time required can be shortened. While one pipette is being analyzed, the next pipette can already be prepared for the next measurement. The entire gas chromatography system will be newly constructed and the mass spectrometer of RGMS is planned to be reused for Auto-RGMS.

5.2 Basic Principles of Gas Chromatography

In the following, a brief introduction to the concepts of gas chromatography relevant to this work is given. This comprises a short description of the adsorption of gases, the characteristics of activated carbons, and a summary of the gas chromatographic process. More thorough discussions can be found in [116], [118], [119] as well as in [120], [121].

Adsorption of Gases

At the surface of a solid, the forces that hold the solid together are unbalanced. Accordingly, when a solid is exposed to a gaseous substance, the molecules or atoms of the substance readily form bonds with the solid and thus become attached to the surface. This process is called *adsorption* and the reverse process is *desorption*. In the special case of noble gases, the substance is bound to the surface only by weak intermolecular van der Waals forces, which is referred to as *physisorption*.

Some important terms related to adsorption are illustrated in fig. 5.2. Adsorption takes place on any solid surface. In this context, the solid is referred to as an *adsorbent*. Materials with high porosity, which have a large total surface area accessible to the gas, are of particular interest for gas chromatography. The pores of an adsorbent are classified based on their inner diameter d as *macropores* ($d > 50$ nm), *mesopores* (2 nm $< d < 50$ nm), and *micropores* ($d < 2$ nm). The substance that is attached to the adsorbent is referred to as *adsorbate*; in the unbound state it is, however, called *adsorptive*.

The amount of gas adsorbed by an adsorbent in equilibrium is described at a constant temperature by the *adsorption isotherm*. A variety of adsorption isotherm models were developed to predict adsorption behavior for different conditions of a system [122]. Since we are interested in the adsorption of very small amounts of gas in this application, the Henry isotherm approximation, valid for low partial pressures P of the gas, is well suited for the following discussions. It states that the number of adsorbed particles n is proportional to P

$$n = HP, \quad (5.1)$$

where H is the Henry coefficient that depends on the temperature, the adsorbent, and the adsorptive.

For a spherical nonpolar molecule on a smooth uniform surface, the Henry constant H for a given temperature T can be calculated [119] as

$$H = \frac{a}{k_{\text{B}}T} \int \left(\exp \left(\frac{-\Phi(z)}{k_{\text{B}}T} \right) - 1 \right) dz. \quad (5.2)$$

Here, $\Phi(z)$ is the potential energy of adsorption as a function of the distance z of the molecule perpendicular to the surface, a is the surface area of the adsorbent per unit of mass, and k_{B} denotes the Boltzmann constant. As the temperature increases, the

Figure 5.2: Illustration of important terms used to describe adsorption. Adapted from [121].

Henry coefficient decreases, thus shifting the adsorption equilibrium to the gas phase. This is a result of the larger average kinetic energy of the adsorbent proportional to $k_B T$. Hence, baking an adsorbent while continuously pumping the gas phase is an efficient method to regenerate and purify the adsorbent. For physisorption, $\Phi(z)$ can be approximated by a Lennard-Jones-like potential whose depth increases with the atomic polarizability. Since H depends exponentially on $\Phi(z)$, even small differences in the adsorption potential can drastically change the adsorption equilibrium. For a realistic adsorbent, one has to consider that the complex structure of a porous surface gives rise to sites with different attraction strengths. The largest adsorption strength can be obtained in micropores, whose inner diameter can be similar to the size of an atom or molecule. In this case, the opposite wall of the micropore contributes to the adsorption, and the particle is trapped by the adsorption potentials of the two walls. A discussion of the choice of the adsorption potential and the modeling of micropores can be found in [120].

Gas Chromatography

Gas chromatography is a method of separating a gas mixture into its constituents that takes advantage of the fact that different gases have different adsorption equilibria. For this, the substance (or *analyte*) to be separated is transported by a chemically inert carrier gas (in our case helium) through a tube filled with some adsorbent (adsorption column). The analyte then distributes between the *mobile phase* (carrier gas) and the *stationary phase* (adsorbent). The distribution between the phases is different for different gas components according to the respective adsorption equilibria, which causes the separation of the components.

Gas chromatography can be modeled by discretization of the continuous process. For this, the column is divided into N consecutive segments, called theoretical plates

Figure 5.3: *Left:* Illustration of the discretization of the gas chromatographic process. The analyte (probe) is transported through the column via the mobile phase. In each plate, the adsorption equilibrium between the stationary phase and the mobile phase is established. *Top right:* At time t_0 , the mixed analyte enters the column. The two components are propagated with different velocities through the column and are thereby separated. Thus, component A exits the column at time t_A before component B exits the column at time $t_B > t_A$. *Bottom right:* With a suitable detector, the chromatogram of this separation can be recorded. $t_A - t_0$ and $t_B - t_0$ are the retention times of the respective components. Adapted from [117].

[123]. The partitioning is chosen so that an equilibrium can be assumed between the adsorbent in the mobile and stationary phases in each theoretical plate. The height of a theoretical plate depends on the column temperature and the average carrier gas velocity. The segmentation of the column is illustrated in fig. 5.3 (left). In the first plate, an equilibrium between the mobile phase and the stationary phase is established according to eq. (5.1). Then, the mobile phase is propagated to the next plate and a new equilibrium is obtained in both plates according to the new partial pressures of the adsorptive in each plate. This process is repeated until the end of the column is reached. The inert carrier gas is not adsorbed and thus flows with a constant velocity through the column. The analyte, in turn, is adsorbed, desorbed, transported, and adsorbed again multiple times and thus propagates through the column at a lower velocity. The different components of the analyte travel through the column at different velocities due to their differently strong interactions with the adsorbent. This is illustrated in fig. 5.3 (top right) for an analyte $A + B$ consisting of two gases A and B . For the separation of xenon and krypton, the larger polarizability of xenon compared to krypton [124] is exploited. This shifts the adsorption equilibrium

towards the stationary phase, resulting in longer retention times of xenon compared to krypton.

In addition to the separation of the constituents, each substance is subject to dispersion effects such as diffusion during transport through the column, which cause a broadening of their concentration in the column. For optimal separation, the dimensions of the column and the system parameters must be tuned to maximize the difference in the propagation times between the substances while minimizing their dispersion.

A *chromatogram* of the separated analyte can be captured with a suitable detector placed at the end of the column (fig. 5.3 bottom right). The baseline corresponds to the constant outflow of carrier gas, which is usually set to zero. If a component of the analyte elutes, a peak is observed. Its area is proportional to the gas amount of this component². The time between the inlet of a sample t_0 and its maximum at the end of the column t_m is defined as the *retention time* t_r of a gas. It depends on the adsorptive, the adsorbent, the system parameters, and the geometry of the column. For fixed conditions, it is characteristic for each gas. As stated above, the width of a peak depends on the dispersion effects during transport. Peaks often exhibit an asymmetric peak shape, which can be caused by a variety of reasons. A theoretical prediction of the expected peak shape is therefore very challenging. However, a common source of asymmetry is the heterogeneous pore size distribution of adsorbents, which gives rise to adsorption sites with varying binding energies. In this case, first, the energetically favorable sites are filled. The desorption probability for a particle adsorbed at such sites is lower compared to the particles that have to fill the energetically less favorable sites. Thus, a fraction of the analyte is transported through the column more slowly than the bulk, resulting in a tail of the peak with long retention times, which is referred to as *tailing*. *Fronting*, on the other hand, describes processes that give rise to a shallow frontal edge. This can, for example, occur when the adsorbent is overloaded or if channels between the adsorbent grains in the column are present.

The power to resolve two consecutive peaks of a chromatogram is defined by the resolution $R = 4(t_{r2} - t_{r1}) / (w_1 + w_2)$ for the retention times $t_{r2} > t_{r1}$ and the peak widths w_1 and w_2 at the inflection points, which correspond to 2σ for Gaussian curves. To account for the asymmetry of the peaks, instead of using the full width of the peak, only the halves of the peaks facing each other are considered in the following:

$$R = \frac{t_{r2} - t_{r1}}{1.7(w_{\text{tail},1} + w_{\text{front},2})}, \quad (5.3)$$

where $w_{\text{tail},1}$ is the half-maximum width of the tail of the first peak and $w_{\text{front},2}$ is the half-maximum width of the front of the second peak. The factor 1.7 accounts for the usage of the half-maximum widths instead of the widths at the inflection points. For peaks of similar height and without tailing, $R = 1.5$ corresponds to a

²depending on the detector used for acquiring the chromatogram, a correction factor might be required to account for the different physical properties of the gas.

6σ separation. In the context of a gas chromatographic separation of krypton and xenon, a high resolution is particularly important. If it is too low, a considerable amount of xenon will bleed into the krypton peak, which would strongly impair the following procedure.

The Adsorbent *ShinCarbon*

In a previous work, a comprehensive study was carried out to find the most suitable adsorbent for the separation of krypton and xenon [117]. *ShinCarbon*, which is a particular activated carbon, proved to be the adsorbent with the most favorable properties. It is therefore being considered for use in Auto-RGMS.

Activated carbons feature surface areas that are among the largest of all adsorbents. They are produced by carbonization of a variety of carbonaceous materials and subsequent activation at elevated temperatures [125]. In this process, the carbon atoms are arranged in randomly stacked aromatic sheets, which gives rise to slit-shaped pores between the sheets. The exact distribution of pores depends on the raw material as well as on the activation procedure. However, it is usually dominated by micropores, which make up around 95 % of the total surface area of the adsorbent [126].

With a special activation procedure or an additional treatment after the activation, it is possible to obtain an activated carbon with a very narrow pore distribution. Such activated carbons are called carbon molecular sieves (CMS). These adsorbents can be used for a very efficient separation of two substances if they have different diameters. Small molecules are strongly adsorbed by the micropores while large molecules cannot access the pores and are thus transported rapidly through the column. The adsorbent *ShinCarbon* belongs to this family of adsorbents. However, the steric effects that lead to the characteristic “sieving” are not relevant for the separation of krypton and xenon, since both atoms have similar diameters. Both noble gases are strongly adsorbed by the micropores of the adsorbent. The separation of the two is simply achieved through the stronger adsorption strength of xenon atoms due to their larger atomic polarizability.

5.3 A Prototype of the Gas Chromatography System for Auto-RGMS

In the context of this work, a test setup was developed and built to demonstrate the feasibility of an automated gas chromatography system. The prototype features automatically controlled carrier gas flow, pressure, and adsorption column temperature. A schematic drawing and a picture of the final test setup are shown in fig. 5.4. A helium bottle supplies a constant carrier gas flow, which is controlled by a mass

flow controller³ (MFC) and additionally monitored by a mass flow meter⁴ (MFM). A gas sample can be injected into the system via a glass pipette, which consists of two volumes divided by three manual valves (V0–V3). For all measurements presented here, a gas mixture of xenon and krypton with a ratio of 10:1 was used. Prior to filling, the volumes $V_1 = (3.560 \pm 0.005) \text{ cm}^3$ and $V_2 = (276.580 \pm 0.007) \text{ cm}^3$ were determined by measuring the mass when filled with water. The pressure upstream of the adsorption column is monitored by a full range vacuum sensor⁵ (P_1) and a pressure sensor⁶ (P_2). Two manual valves V6 and V7 connect the adsorption column to the system. It is filled with $(2.580 \pm 0.025) \text{ g}$ of *ShinCarbon* adsorbent such that the level in both arms of the column is equal. The automatic temperature control of the column is realized by a heating and a cooling system. It consists of two heating elements (H1), two PT1000 temperature sensors (PT1–2), and an LN₂ dewar that is weighed by a load cell W1 and can be filled by opening the magnetic valve MV1. A thermal conductivity detector⁷ (TCD) is mounted to acquire the chromatogram of the gas separation procedure. The pressure downstream of the column is measured using a pressure sensor⁸ (P_3). This end of the system is pumped by a scroll pump. The outlet flow rate and thus the pressure P_3 can be finely adjusted by the control valve CV1⁹. The sensors MFM, TCD, W1, PT1–2, P_1 and P_3 , as well as the heater H1 and the valves CV1 and MV1, are connected to a computer via a compact DAQ system¹⁰. The sensors are read out, and the valves and heater are controlled via a custom LabView application. In the following, more detail is provided for the most important subsystems and instruments and the operation procedure is summarized.

5.3.1 Automated Control of Carrier Gas Flow, Pressure, and Column Temperature

To obtain constant and reproducible conditions during the separation procedure, the helium flow, pressure P_3 , and temperature of the adsorption column are automatically controlled. For this purpose, proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control loops are employed. To maintain a measured process variable $y(t)$ at a specified set point $r(t)$, a process parameter – such as the opening of a valve or the current of a heating element – is adjusted based on the control variable $u(t)$. It is defined as the weighted sum of a proportional (P), integral (I), and derivative (D) term

$$u(t) = K_p \left(e(t) + \frac{1}{T_i} \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + T_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \right). \quad (5.4)$$

³Tylan FC-2901

⁴mks GM50A001202RB3020

⁵Pfeiffer PKR 361, Hochstrom, DN 40 CF-F

⁶Greisinger MSD 2,5 BAE

⁷GOW-MAC 10-470

⁸Wika WU - 20

⁹Swagelok Stainless Steel Metering Bellows Sealed Valve with Gulex drive / VAT all-metal variable leak valve series 59.0

¹⁰National Instruments NI cDAQ-9188XT

Figure 5.4: Schematic drawing (top) and picture (bottom) of the prototype of an automated gas chromatography system for Auto-RGMS. The helium flow through the system is controlled by a mass flow controller (MFC) and monitored by a mass flow meter (MFM). The chromatogram is obtained using a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and the pressure P_3 is controlled by means of a control valve (CV1). The temperature of the column is regulated by a heating element (H1), two thermal sensors (PT1-2), and an LN₂ dewar that is automatically refilled via a magnetic valve (MV1) once the weight measured by a load cell (W1) drops below a threshold value. The gas sample is injected via a pipette that consists of two volumes divided by the three manual valves V0–V2.

Each term is a function of the error value $e(t) = r(t) - y(t)$. The proportional gain K_p , integral time T_i and derivative time T_d specify the controller response and are tuned to the desired behavior.

In the final prototype, the pressure of the gas chromatography system P_3 is regulated via the PID-controlled valve CV1. A constant carrier gas flow of around $100 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ STP/min}$ needs to be provided during the separation. Since a larger flow leads to shorter retention times, the stability of this parameter is important. An MFC was used to achieve this in the final version of the setup.

The adsorption column needs to be operated at temperatures in a range between about $-200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during sample freezing and about $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during bake-out. During the separation process, a temperature between about $-100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and up to $0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ must be maintained at a constant level with high accuracy over a period of several hours. This is crucial to ensure reproducible retention times for krypton and xenon. To achieve this in an automated way, the adsorption column is enclosed in a solid copper block together with two heating elements (H1) and two PT1000 temperature sensors (PT1–2). This copper block is insulated by a PTFE shielding and immersed in a movable LN_2 dewar. The PTFE shielding prevents strong temperature gradients on the copper surface. The averaged temperature measured by the sensors PT1 and PT2 is regulated by adjusting the current through the heating elements with a PID controller. To control temperatures above room temperature, the heated copper block is removed from the LN_2 dewar. The final version of the prototype features an automated refill system for the LN_2 dewar. For this, the LN_2 level of the dewar is measured by a load cell (W1), which is placed below the dewar. LN_2 from a reservoir can be filled into the dewar by opening the magnetic valve MV1. With a two-point controller, the LN_2 level is kept between two set values.

5.3.2 Thermal Conductivity Detector

The chromatogram of the test setup is acquired with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). This detector is orders of magnitude less sensitive than the mass spectrometer used in RGMS. However, it is being considered to include a TCD in Auto-RGMS for quality assurance. The gas sample used for the proof of concept of a stable separation process has a much larger krypton concentration ($\text{Xe:Kr} = 10:1$) than in a typical sample measured by the RGMS. This way, the sensitivity of the TCD is sufficient to detect both components of the gas mixture.

The TCD used in this setup consists of two tubes with thermistors, one of which is flushed by the inflow into the column and the other by the outflow from the column. If the heat capacity of the outflowing gas is reduced by eluting krypton or xenon¹¹, the temperature of the thermistor will rise as a consequence of the less efficient heat draining. This will lower the resistance of the thermistor, which is measured as a voltage drop U_{TCD} via a Wheatstone bridge. The signal is, in first approximation,

¹¹The thermal conductivity of helium at 400 K is a factor ~ 15 times larger than that of krypton and a factor ~ 26 times larger than xenon [118].

proportional to the concentration of the analyte but also depends on the relative heat capacity of the analyte and carrier gas (see, e.g., [118]).

5.3.3 Operation of the Automated Gas Chromatography System

Before each measurement, the adsorption column is heated to 150 °C and flushed with 20 cm³STP/min helium at $P_3 = 1200$ mbar. After at least 10 minutes, the heating elements are switched off and the column is immersed in LN₂ to cool down. Once the temperature sensors indicate a constant temperature about -200 °C, the helium flow is stopped and the entire volume downstream of the MFC is evacuated. A gas sample is then injected into the calibration volume confined by the valve within MFC, V3, and V6. In a dedicated measurement, the calibration volume was determined to be $V_{\text{cal}} = (51.3 \pm 0.4)$ cm³ based on the knowledge of V_3 of the pipette. This allows the size of the sample to be calculated by measuring the pressure P_2 and the ambient temperature. Then, a sample of desired size is frozen onto the cold adsorbent column. The helium flow for the separation is then set at a pressure $P_3 = 1200$ mbar. As soon as the control parameters are stable, the warm-up procedure of the adsorption column is initiated. This is the starting point of the chromatogram. As the temperature approaches the desired constant value for separation, the PID controller is turned on to keep the temperature stable. Figure 5.5 shows a typical chromatogram and the three controlled system parameters. One can see that already during the warm-up phase, two peaks emerge. These correspond to O₂ and N₂, which inevitably contaminate the sample due to small leaks of the pipette valves. After that, a narrow peak from eluting krypton can be seen. On a time scale from 15 minutes to several hours later, the xenon peak emerges, which is characterized by a long tail. Once both components of the gas sample have eluted, the acquisition is stopped and the setup is prepared for the next measurement by heating the column to 150 °C and flushing it with helium.

Figure 5.5: Example of a measurement during the gas separation procedure. The chromatogram is shown in the top panel. Below, the three controlled system parameters are shown as a function of time.

5.4 Measurements and Tests

During the development of the automatic gas chromatography system, various gas separations were performed. This allowed testing the stability of the automatically controlled system parameters under realistic conditions while at the same time gaining some information on the new adsorbent candidate for Auto-RGMS. In addition, a leak valve was tested for its suitability as a control valve for Auto-RGMS.

5.4.1 Measurements with the Automated Gas Chromatography System

The setup shown in fig. 5.4 corresponds to v2.1 of the test setup, which was used for most of the measurements presented in this work. However, the separation procedure has also been performed with other versions of the prototype. The first version of the test setup v1.0 was only used to set up the PID control and test the thermal conductivity detector. In version v1.1, the control valve was located upstream of the adsorption column to control the helium flow. In this setup, the pressure P_3 was adjusted manually with a needle valve. Also, the temperature was controlled manually by adjusting the current through the heating elements with a potentiometer and the LN₂ dewar was regularly refilled by hand. In version v2.0, the temperature control was automated and the MFC was introduced to replace the control valve upstream of the adsorption column. Furthermore, the needle valve was replaced by a control valve to automatically control P_3 . The automated filling of the LN₂ dewar was added in version v2.1 and in version v2.2, a different control valve was used for CV1.

An overview of the runs performed with the test setup of version v1.1 and later is presented in table 5.1. Columns 1 to 3 show the run number, version, and sample size V_s . In columns 4 to 6, the averages of the controlled system parameters are shown during the time from the rise of the krypton peak to the tail of the xenon peak. The error for each value is given by the standard deviation of the parameter. Columns 7 to 9 show parameters that characterize the chromatogram. The krypton retention time $t_{r,Kr}$ is defined as the time from the rise of temperature above $T = -190$ °C until the maximum of the krypton peak is reached. The xenon retention time is defined analogously and the difference between the two times is denoted as Δt . The resolution of the two peaks is calculated according to eq. (5.3). The errors of the parameters of the chromatogram are obtained based on the uncertainty of the retention time of a peak due to fluctuations of the TCD voltage. These errors are estimated using the time range corresponding to the 99th percentile of the peaks' voltage. The relative errors of the system parameters for each run are visualized in fig. 5.6. Replacing the PID control loop with a leak valve by a dedicated MFC from version v2.0 on reduces the relative error of the helium flow by about an order of magnitude to values as low as 0.03%. For the pressure P_3 , an acceptably low relative error below 1% is obtained with all versions of the setup. However, the lowest relative error of 0.08% is achieved with version v2.2 with a *Swagelok Stainless Steel Metering Bellows Sealed*

Figure 5.6: Relative errors of the controlled system parameters as a function of the run number. The colored bands indicate the version number of the prototype. The relative error of the helium flow F was reduced by an order of magnitude by using a dedicated mass flow controller from version v2.0 onwards. The stability of the pressure P_3 is acceptably low in all versions. An improvement in the stability of the column temperature T from v2.1 onwards was achieved by improving the PID-controller and adding an automatic LN₂ refill system.

Valve with Gulex drive (in the following referred to as MV). An improvement in the PID control loop and the added automatic LN₂ refill system result in improved column temperature stability from version v2.1 with a relative error below 0.8% including the lowest value of 0.13% in run 15. The automated control of the helium flow, pressure, and temperature of the adsorption column is discussed in more detail in section 5.4.2. The conclusions drawn from the chromatograms acquired in each run are discussed in section 5.4.3.

5.4.2 Automated Control of Carrier Gas Flow, Pressure, and Column Temperature

All components of Auto-RGMS must comply with high leak tightness requirements. Therefore, it is envisaged to use only fully metal-sealed valves in the system. However, control valves designed for the desired low flow rates between 10 cm³STP/min and 200 cm³STP/min are usually PTFE sealed. As an alternative, a fully metal-sealed

Table 5.1: Summary of the results of the measurements that were performed with the test setup. The provided values of the controlled system parameters correspond to their average values between the rise of the krypton peak and the end of the xenon peak (end of the acquisition). *v1.1:* PID controlled leak valve for mass flow control, and manual needle valve to set P_3 ; *v2.0:* MFC, PID controlled leak valve to control P_3 , and PID controlled temperature; *v2.1:* MFC, PID controlled leak valve to control P_3 , PID controlled temperature, and automated LN₂ refill; *v2.2:* MFC, PID controlled metering valve to control P_3 , PID controlled temperature, and automated LN₂ refill.

Run Nr.	Setup	V_s [cm ³ STP]	T [°C]	System Parameters			Chromatogram Results			
				P_3 [mbar]	F [cm ³ STP/min]	$t_{r,kr}$ [min]	Δt [min]	R		
6	v1.1	2.64 ± 0.08	-9.2 ± 1.6	1203 ± 9	50.1 ± 0.6	34.64 ± 0.15	103 ± 3	13 ± 8		
7	v1.1	2.57 ± 0.08	-13 ± 6	1245.0 ± 2.6	150.0 ± 0.6	26.637 ± 0.022	35.8 ± 0.4	13 ± 3		
8	v2.0	3.12 ± 0.06	-30.7 ± 2.3	1201 ± 5	149.98 ± 0.04	17.01 ± 0.04	116.6 ± 0.3	13.8 ± 0.9		
9	v2.0	3.07 ± 0.06	-5 ± 9	1201 ± 4	150.02 ± 0.05	11.166 ± 0.010	30.17 ± 0.14	15.0 ± 1.8		
10	v2.0	3.02 ± 0.06	-60.1 ± 0.9	1207.8 ± 2.7	150.07 ± 0.05	35.41 ± 0.14	> 508	N/A		
11	v2.1	5.90 ± 0.10	-0.9 ± 2.1	1198 ± 7	149.34 ± 0.08	12.905 ± 0.020	19.21 ± 0.20	13 ± 3		
12	v2.1	1.46 ± 0.05	-0.5 ± 1.4	1208.4 ± 2.2	150.30 ± 0.04	12.933 ± 0.025	28.6 ± 0.3	15 ± 4		
13	v2.1	2.81 ± 0.05	-0.5 ± 1.4	1200 ± 4	149.74 ± 0.05	11.812 ± 0.022	23.9 ± 0.3	14 ± 4		
14	v2.1	11.17 ± 0.13	-0.0 ± 0.9	1202 ± 4	149.89 ± 0.04	10.672 ± 0.013	14.20 ± 0.18	9.2 ± 1.9		
15	v2.1	2.70 ± 0.05	-50.0 ± 0.3	1201 ± 3	149.81 ± 0.17	24.01 ± 0.15	438 ± 32	N/A		
16	v2.2	2.65 ± 0.05	-0.2 ± 1.4	1200.0 ± 0.9	149.96 ± 0.09	12.103 ± 0.022	23.8 ± 0.4	15 ± 6		

leak valve¹² (LV) is considered to control the pressure and mass flow in Auto-RGMS. It is equipped with a diaphragm sealing that is controlled with a spring-loaded piston. The position of the piston and thus the force acting on the diaphragm can be controlled with a stepper motor in a range of 100 000 steps. This allows for a precise adjustment of the gas flow in a wide range from 1×10^{-10} mbarl/s to 500 mbarl/s. Leak valves are usually used for calibrating leak detectors and not for controlling gas flows. Therefore, before operating it as a control valve, tests were performed to roughly characterize the LV, which are summarized in appendix C.

For runs 6 and 7, the LV was used to control the helium mass flow. For this, the motor position of the valve was adjusted by a PI-control loop with $K_p = 0.05$ and $T_i = 0.001$ min based on the flow measured by the MFM. Two measurements with flows of $F = (50.13 \pm 0.63)$ cm³STP/min (set point 50 cm³STP/min) and $F = (150.02 \pm 0.55)$ sccm/min (set point 150 cm³STP/min) were performed. With 1.3 % and 0.37 %, the relative errors are acceptably low. For run 7, control parameters together with the motor position of the valve are shown as a function of time in fig. 5.7 (left). One can see that during warm-up, the valve opened gradually to maintain a constant flow. This could be explained by a larger flow resistance of the adsorbent at higher temperatures. The full range exploited by the motor during this measurement was only about 200 out of the 100 000 steps. Although the relative error of the mass flow is rather small, deviations of more than 10 % from the setpoint are observed for short time intervals in both runs, which can be seen as a spiky structure in fig. 5.7 (left). Those occur after strong overcorrections of slight drifts of the flow. The reason why this occasionally happened, while the parameter control was otherwise stable most of the time, could not be definitively identified. However, a hysteresis observed in a pre-test (fig. C.2 in appendix C) could at least explain part of the response. Most likely, the behavior could be improved by fine-tuning the PI-controller or limiting the step rate of the motor. However, due to the large performance improvement achieved with an MFC of almost one order of magnitude, the plan of controlling the helium flow with the LV was discarded. Since the MFC is PTFE-sealed, it must, however, be placed in front of T1 in Auto-RGMS. The feasibility of this remains to be shown.

In runs 8 to 15, the pressure P_3 was controlled at 1200 mbar using the LV, which was placed between the pump and the column outlet as shown in fig. 5.4. A simple proportional controller with $K_p = 5$ was used for this purpose, which showed damped oscillatory behavior when the pressure was set at low temperatures but was otherwise reliable and stable. Various controllers with additional integral and derivative terms performed well at high temperatures but turned out to be unstable at the lowest temperature, for which the flow resistance of the column decreased. The relative error of P_3 achieved with this setup is below 0.6 % in all runs. The control parameters and motor position of the valve for the longest uninterrupted operation of over 12 hours (run 15) are shown as a function of time in fig. 5.7. One can see that only about 50 out of the 100 000 motor steps are used for controlling P_3 . Individual steps of the valve motor cause a change in pressure of up to 15 mbar. In other cases, the pressure

¹²VAT all-metal variable leak valve series 59.0

Figure 5.7: Motor position of the leak valve (LV pos.) and system parameters during gas separation as a function of time. **Left:** Control of the helium flow F at $150 \text{ cm}^3\text{STP}/\text{min}$ with the LV (run 7). Even though the relative error is reasonably low, deviations of over 10 % from the setpoint occur for short periods of time. **Right:** Control of the pressure P_3 at 1200 mbar with the LV (run 15). For over 12 hours, the pressure was maintained sufficiently constant.

is barely affected by a change of the motor position, which can be explained by the hysteresis observed for the valve (see appendix C). Nevertheless, the performance of pressure control with the LV was good, and no instabilities were observed in eight runs, as was the case when operating as a mass flow controller. In run 17, the LV was substituted by the metering valve (MV), which has the smallest opening of all the fully metal-sealed control valves. It was controlled by a PID controller with $K_p = 5$, $T_i = 0.4 \text{ min}$ and $T_d = 0.05 \text{ min}$ and achieved an even better performance than the LV with a relative error of only 0.08 %. Moreover, this system showed considerably improved accuracy and stability when setting the pressure at low temperatures. In a separate measurement, the helium flow was varied manually while keeping constant pressure with the PID-controlled MV. The pressure could be reliably maintained constant even with a helium flow of only $10 \text{ cm}^3\text{STP}/\text{min}$. For these reasons, the MV will be used in Auto-RGMS to automatically control P_3 if the helium flow of the final

design will be above $10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{STP}/\text{min}$. It was demonstrated that the pressure control via the LV can be a good alternative in case only lower helium flows are achievable, for example, due to the use of a different adsorbent.

For all measurements summarized in table 5.1, the adsorption column was operated at almost -200°C during sample freezing and about 200°C during bake-out. During separation, constant temperatures in the range between -60°C and 0°C were controlled with high accuracy below 1%. For this, the current through the heating elements was adjusted by a PID-control loop with $K_p = 0.03$, $T_i = 2.0 \text{ min}$ and $T_d = 0.7 \text{ min}$. Positive values of $u(t)$ defined in eq. (5.4), which cause an increase in current, were scaled by a factor of 10^{-4} . This measure successfully countered the observed asymmetric temperature response of the system to a change in current. Specifically, a faster temperature change was seen after an increase in current compared to the temperature change after a decrease in current of the same absolute value. The automated refill LN_2 system, which was added in version v2.1, allowed an autonomous operation during separation and helped improve the temperature stability. The LN_2 consumption was about 3 kg h^{-1} at 0°C .

5.4.3 Analysis of the Chromatograms

Columns 7 and 8 in table 5.1 show the krypton retention time $t_{r,\text{Kr}}$ and the separation time between the krypton and xenon peak Δt for all runs. The krypton retention time ranges from about 10 minutes for $T \simeq 0^\circ\text{C}$ to about 35 minutes for $T \simeq -60^\circ\text{C}$. The shortest separation time between krypton and xenon is observed in run 14 with under 15 minutes, which is discussed in more detail below. For run 10 with $T \simeq -60^\circ\text{C}$, even nine hours after the start of the chromatogram, no xenon peak was observed, so the column was heated. Then, a very clear peak emerged. However, part of the xenon may have already eluted earlier at a rate below the detection limit of the TCD. For runs 13 and 16, the setpoints of the temperature, helium flow, and pressure were identical and the sample size was comparable. The measured krypton retention times of $(11.812 \pm 0.022) \text{ min}$ and $(12.103 \pm 0.022) \text{ min}$ deviate by less than 20 seconds, which approximately corresponds to the full width half maximum (FWHM) of the peaks. The differences between krypton and xenon retention times Δt of both runs agree within their errors. This illustrates the reproducibility of chromatograms, which can be achieved with the automated system. The largest inaccuracy likely results from slight variations in the temperature profiles during warm-up. This is observed for separation procedures with the same temperatures and is believed to be caused by subtle differences in the manually initiated warm-up procedures. Also, the level of the LN_2 dewar at the beginning of the warm-up process varied between the runs. In future measurements, a higher reproducibility of the temperature profiles could be achieved by implementing a fully automated warm-up script, which would include refilling the LN_2 dewar just before initiating the heating.

In the last column of table 5.1, the peak resolution R is shown, which is approximately constant above 13 for most runs. For run 15, the lower temperature of $(-50.0 \pm 0.3)^\circ\text{C}$ gives rise to a separation time of over seven hours. At the same time,

Figure 5.8: The chromatograms of four runs with the same system parameters but varying sample sizes are aligned at an adsorption column temperature of -50°C to illustrate the decreasing retention time of xenon for larger gas samples. The tails of the xenon peak appear to have a common envelope function. The inset plot shows the differences in the krypton and xenon retention times Δt as a function of the sample size.

however, the width of the peaks strongly increases. Due to the limited resolution of the TCD, the width of the xenon peak cannot be defined properly, thus the calculation of R is spared. Likewise, the resolution for run 10 cannot be calculated since no xenon peak was observed at -60°C . For run 14, a value of only $R = (9.2 \pm 1.9)$ is observed, which can be attributed to a dependence of the chromatogram on the sample size, as discussed in more detail below. In conclusion, for all acquired chromatograms, the achieved separation is sufficiently good for the application in Auto-RGMS, which is in line with the results obtained in [117].

In the same study, it was observed that for *ShinCarbon*, the retention time of xenon depends on the sample size [117]. To verify and further investigate this peculiar behavior, four measurements at the same temperature $T = 0^\circ\text{C}$, pressure $P_3 = 1200 \text{ mbar}$ and helium flow $F = 150 \text{ cm}^3\text{STP}$ were performed for varying sample sizes between $1.46 \text{ cm}^3\text{STP}$ and $11.17 \text{ cm}^3\text{STP}$. The individual chromatograms are aligned to reach $T = -50^\circ\text{C}$ at the time $t = 0 \text{ min}$. This alleviates a shift of the chromatograms due to slight variations of the temperature curves, which can be seen

in the lower panel of fig. 5.8. The choice of $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is motivated by the very long xenon retention time observed for this temperature. The aligned chromatograms are shown in the upper panel of fig. 5.8. Similar to the observations in [117], the xenon retention time becomes shorter for an increasing sample size. An interesting characteristic that was not observed before is that the tails of the four xenon peaks seem to have a common envelope function. For krypton, the retention times remain approximately constant. A small discrepancy is observed, which might be attributed to the variation of the temperature curves.

The origin of the strong dependence of the xenon retention time on the sample size is so far not understood. The observed common envelope of the xenon tails could be an indication of saturation effects of xenon in the adsorbent. A possible explanation would be that a small fraction of xenon atoms finds adsorption sites with particularly large adsorption strength, such as micropores that match the atomic diameter of the atom [120]. Xenon atoms that find these sites are propagated more slowly through the column and thus give rise to a tail. If the sample size is increased, the additional xenon atoms will only find adsorption sites with lower adsorption power and are thus eluted more quickly through the column, causing an earlier xenon breakthrough. The observation that the krypton peak does not appear to exhibit the same behavior could be explained by its slightly smaller atomic diameter. Due to the particularly narrow pore size distribution of CMS, it is conceivable that there are no pores as perfectly suitable for krypton as for xenon.

In future studies, it would be interesting to repeat the measurements with higher accuracy of the warm-up curves to learn more about a possible variation of the krypton retention time with the sample size. Also, an effect due to the interaction of xenon with the other components of the gas mixture cannot be excluded. To investigate this, one could repeat the same procedures only with one gas component. To achieve this, a new leak-tight pipette would be needed. To verify the working hypothesis that the observed effect can be explained by the abundance of a particular pore size in *ShinCarbon*, similar studies could be performed with other CMS adsorbents with slightly different pore size distributions.

5.5 Current Status and Future Prospects of Auto-RGMS

A prototype of an automated gas chromatography system for Auto-RGMS was developed and operated in this work. In this context, various components were tested to be used in Auto-RGMS. The stability and reliability of the system were assessed under realistic conditions during 11 separation procedures. Relative errors during separation as low as 0.13 % for the adsorption column temperature, 0.08 % for the pressure, and 0.03 % for the helium flow were achieved. The automated temperature control of the adsorption column has proven to work reliably for separation temperatures between $-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ as well as during cool-down at almost $-200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and

bake-out at 200 °C. The slight variations of the temperature curves observed during warm-up can likely be overcome by fully automating the warm-up procedure. This is expected to enhance the reproducibility of retention times of the individual sample components. Moreover, it must be shown in a future measurement that maintaining constant carrier gas flows is also possible if the MFC is operated upstream of column T1. The test runs performed during the development of the prototype were used to verify a previously observed dependence of the separation time of krypton and xenon on the sample size. The new measurements indicate saturation effects of the adsorbent, but more research is needed to better understand the origin of this effect.

After completing the test runs with the prototype, the adsorption column was baked out and pumped, and then connected to the mass spectrometer of the RGMS. In this way, it is possible to determine whether the column can regenerate sufficiently after being exposed to a sample. The first results indicate that despite the higher maximal temperature of *ShinCarbon*, the remaining noble gas contamination is too high. This might be caused by the strong adsorption power of the small micropores in CMS. Further tests will be performed to assess if the contamination can be reduced to a sufficiently low level. If this is not the case, a new test campaign must be performed to find a suitable adsorbent for Auto-RGMS. The final version of the prototype could be reused to perform numerous measurements with minimal effort.

Although the definitive decision on the adsorbent used in Auto-RGMS has not yet been made, construction of the new temperature-controlled adsorption columns is underway. Beyond that, all important decisions about the design of the Auto-RGMS were made, so construction of the rest of the system can begin soon.

6 Summary and Conclusions

Astronomical and cosmological studies provide compelling indirect evidence for the existence of dark matter (DM) in our universe, which accounts for more than 25 % of its total matter and energy content. So far, the most sensitive detectors have not been able to directly detect any particle that could explain the otherwise puzzling observations. For this reason, scientists strive to develop detectors with ever-higher sensitivity to explore hitherto untested regions of the parameter spaces of various particle DM candidates. The XENONnT experiment aims to unravel the nature of DM by directly detecting weakly interacting massive particles (WIMPs). For this purpose, the experiment operates a dual-phase xenon time projection chamber (TPC) with an active liquid xenon (LXe) target of 5.9 t. It is expected to be sensitive to spin-independent WIMP-nucleon interactions with a cross-section of $1.4 \times 10^{-48} \text{ cm}^2$ for a WIMP with a mass of $50 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ [15]. This is more than an order of magnitude beyond the current best limit [38]. The DARWIN collaboration aims to improve the sensitivity by another order of magnitude with a future LXe detector [41], [42]. Achieving such sensitivities places high demands on a variety of tasks from different areas of expertise. In this work, three aspects of the direct search for DM were explored. The results contribute to the basic characterization of the detector, the statistical evaluation of its data, and the measurement of intrinsic backgrounds.

In chapter 3, the existence of a volume in the TPC of XENONnT was verified, which is insensitive to the charge signal of a particle interaction. Gamma-ray events from an external calibration source and alpha particles interactions from intrinsic ^{222}Rn background were examined. All data validate the existence of a charge insensitive volume (CIV), in which the charge signal is completely lost, and a related partial charge loss volume (PCLV), in which a fraction of the signal is retained, during the first science run of XENONnT. The largest charge loss was observed in the lower outer part of the TPC. An angular dependence of the CIV and PCLV was found that hints toward different wall charge-up in different segments of the TPC wall. Using alpha particle interactions with a spatially uniform distribution, the masses of the CIV and PCLV with charge loss of more than 50 % were estimated to be $(120 \pm 4) \text{ kg}$ and $(56 \pm 3) \text{ kg}$, respectively. Both values are higher than the expectation from field simulations. Together, CIV and PCLV account for about 3 % of the active volume in the studied region of the TPC, which is about twice as large as expected. Much larger volumes could be excluded by all studies. A modified fiducial volume was proposed, which rejects more than 85 % of events that exhibit partial charge loss with a nominal fiducial mass above 4 t. This could be employed for calibration measurements to alleviate a bias due to impaired signals from the PCLV.

The presented study provides a map of the CIV and PCLV in the first science run of XENONnT and the developed framework can be used to quickly assess the existence and extent of similar volumes in future science runs. However, to precisely estimate the effects of the CIV and PCLV on the analysis, a complete data-driven model would be required. To achieve this, the existing study could be refined. This would include optimizing the event selection and obtaining higher statistics, both of which are feasible. A data-driven model could be used to correct for the bias of the reconstructed position induced by the charge loss volume and enhance the model of the surface background in XENONnT. Furthermore, it would be interesting to investigate the origin of the observed non-uniformity of ^{210}Po events on the TPC wall. Understanding the underlying effect could unlock doors for surface-background reduction.

Goodness-of-fit (GOF) tests are important statistical tools for the data analysis of XENONnT and other experiments. Until now, no streamlined process for GOF testing existed in the XENON collaboration. To fill this void, a publicly available software suite was developed, which provides a variety of binned and unbinned GOF tests and calculates the corresponding p-values without assuming asymptotic behavior of the test statistic.

As described in chapter 4, the software was used in this work to find sensitive GOF tests to identify fits with incomplete models to typical recoil band data. First, the influence of the choice of the binning on the test result was studied. An unreliable behavior was observed and investigated for binned tests with equidistant bin edges. This was shown to be related to expected values below one in individual bins and could result in a complete loss of sensitivity of the test. An irregular binning scheme that partitions the fit probability distribution function into bins of equal probability content was discussed and investigated to overcome this problem. The second part of the chapter focused on a systematic toy model analysis to test the performance of various binned and unbinned GOF tests for the analysis of fits to recoil bands. It was demonstrated that, among the studied tests, the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test and Pearson's χ^2 test using the irregular binning scheme are best suited for this purpose.

The developed software is widely used by analysts in the collaboration, and the GOF tests with the best performance in the toy model analysis will be used to validate the fits of the XENONnT DM search. To further improve the sensitivity of binned GOF tests, it would be interesting to investigate the optimal binning parameters for recoil band analyses in more detail and, in particular, to explore the possibilities of other irregular binning schemes. Moreover, sensitive unbinned multi-dimensional GOF tests are vital for multivariate analyses. It would therefore be important to extend the toy model analysis to find suitable unbinned tests.

One of the major challenges of direct DM detection is the mitigation of radioactive backgrounds. Beyond their reduction, it is critical to precisely quantify the remaining backgrounds to build a robust background model. To meet the requirements of the next-generation DM detector proposed by the DARWIN collaboration,

a fully automated rare gas mass spectrometer (Auto-RGMS) for the krypton assay in xenon is envisaged.

As described in chapter 5, a prototype of the automated gas chromatography system of Auto-RGMS was developed, built, and tested for a proof of concept. The stability of the setup during operation was demonstrated under realistic conditions and various components to be used in Auto-RGMS were tested. Relative errors for pressure, adsorption column temperature, and carrier gas flow as low as 0.08 %, 0.13 %, and 0.03 %, were achieved. Based on the good performance of the prototype, the gas chromatography system for Auto-RGMS will be realized according to this design.

In addition to the feasibility study, the setup was used to verify and further investigate an unexpected dependence of the retention time of xenon on the gas amount, which had previously been observed. The observations suggest saturation effects of the adsorbent. However, further studies are needed to verify this conjecture. Therefore, it would be essential to improve the accuracy of the temperature profile during warm-up. It may be necessary to conduct a measurement campaign to find a more suitable adsorbent for the gas chromatography system of Auto-RGMS. For this purpose, the prototype could provide a means for performing many measurements with minimal time and effort.

Appendices

A Mean and Variance of χ^2 Test Statistic Distributions

Figure A.1 shows the mean and variance of $g(T|H_0)$ as a function of y for uniformly distributed toy data that was binned with $k = 20\,000$ bins. For each value of y , the empirical distribution of the test statistic was attained by 1000 toy experiments, as discussed in section 4.1.4. This was repeated for a range of N_0 to obtain the mean and variance of the distribution as a function of y .

For the Poisson likelihood χ^2 test, the mean of the distribution approaches zero for low y . It increases for larger y , overshoots the expected mean from its asymptotic value, and has a maximum at $y \simeq 1.3$. For larger values, the mean then asymptotically approaches $\bar{T} = k$, which corresponds to $\bar{T}/k = 1$ in the plot. The variance of the distribution shown in the lower panels of fig. A.1 is below the asymptotic value of $\text{Var}(T)/k = 2$ for small y . It increases for increasing y , overshoots, and has a global maximum at $y \simeq 3$ from which it approaches its asymptotic value. For Pearson's χ^2 test, the mean of the distribution is independent of y . However, the variance diverges for $y < 1$, which causes some fluctuation also for the mean value for low values of y . Evidently, for both χ^2 GOF tests, the chi-square-distribution is not a good approximation of $g(T|H_0)$ for small expected values y .

Figure A.1: Mean \bar{T} and variance $\text{Var}(T)$ of the test statistic distribution as a function of the expected value in each bin y of a uniform distribution. Both values are normalized by the number of bins k , which are varied to modify y . For the Poisson likelihood χ^2 , the mean and variance are close to zero for low values of y and approach the asymptotic values $\bar{T}/k = 1$ and $\text{Var}(T)/k = 2$ for $y > 10$. For Pearson's χ^2 , the mean is constant at $\bar{T}/k = 1$. The variance strongly increases with decreasing y for $y < 1$ and follows a power law for $y < 10^{-1}$.

B Equiprobably Binned Data

To illustrate the fits with incomplete models, the equiprobably binned histograms for the five reference models are shown in fig. B.1 for parent model 1. For the parent model and the unconditional fit, the number of counts of the toy data in each bin agrees with the expected value within statistical uncertainties. For the fits with incomplete models, a clear deviation in the form of an excess or deficiency at the edges of the recoil band can be observed. This is most apparent in the fit with fixed PY. Here, the data generated from a model with $PY = 0.8$ is shifted to the lower right in $cS1 - \log_{10} cS2$ space with respect to the fit PDF with $PY = 0$. This gives rise to a large excess below and a similarly large deficiency above the recoil band. Similarly, for the fit with fixed MMF one can observe an excess of events below the recoil band for $cS1 < 40$ PE since the fit cannot model the signal-like tail of the toy data without varying MMF. For the fit with fixed RF, the broader distribution in $\log_{10} cS2$ of the data gives rise to an excess of events at the upper and lower edge of the recoil band. The same plots are shown for parent model 2 in fig. B.2.

Figure B.1: Example of one equiprobably binned data set for the five different references for parent model 1. The scale of the color bar is chosen such that bins with number of counts equal to the expectation value in a bin are filled white. An excess (deficiency) to the expectation is shown in red (blue).

Figure B.2: Same as fig. B.1 but for parent model 2.

C Characterization of the VAT Leak Valve

For the characterization of the *VAT all-metal variable leak valve series 59.0* (LV), a simple experimental setup was prepared with the LV, a pressure sensor (P), a pump, and a manual valve (V1), as sketched in the inset of fig. C.1. With a closed LV, the calibration volume V_{cal} was evacuated. Then, V1 was closed and the LV was opened to a specific position of the stepper motor to measure the linear pressure increase from an inflow of the sample gas over time. This procedure was repeated for various positions of the motor to obtain the rate of pressure increase as a function of the stepper motor position as shown in fig. C.1. This allowed air to enter the system, resulting in a linear increase in pressure P , as shown in the inset plot in fig. C.1. A linear function is fit to the data to obtain the slope for each position of the LV motor. For practical purposes, instead of connecting a pipette, this end of the LV was simply opened to ambient air, which acts as a sample reservoir with a constant pressure of about 1000 mbar. For motor positions below $\sim 38\,000$, which corresponds to 38% of the full range, no leak was observed, which means that the leak rate is small compared to the residual pressure of about 1×10^{-4} mbar. Between the motor positions of 39 000 steps and 60 000 steps, rates of pressure increase between $2.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mbar s}^{-1}$ and 82 mbar s^{-1} are measured, which increases roughly exponentially between 42 000 and 51 000 steps. This test indicates that only a small fraction of the full range of the LV is usable for controlling constant flow and pressure.

The same test setup was used to investigate hysteresis of the LV. For this, V1 was opened to constantly pump the volume and the motor position was switched between 43 600, 44 950, and 46 000. The measured pressure profile is shown in fig. C.2. It can be seen that the equilibrium pressure, and thus the size of the leak, is different when the motor position is approached from above or from below. Furthermore, after the valve was fully closed, the equilibrium pressures for all three motor positions are shifted. The observed hysteresis could give rise to instabilities when operated as a control valve.

Figure C.1: Linear pressure increase as a function of the motor position of the leak valve (LV). The setup used for this test is illustrated in the lower inset. For each data point, V_{cal} was evacuated and then filled with the sample gas by opening the LV. The linear pressure increase in V_{cal} is measured and fit for different motor positions of the LV. An example for motor position 42 000 is shown in the upper inset plot.

Figure C.2: The equilibrium pressures resulting from different leaks in a constantly pumped system are shown. The leaks are realized by three different positions of the leak valve (LV) motor. The equilibrium pressure for the motor position 44 950 changes when it is approached from above or below. After the valve was completely closed (motor position 0), the equilibrium pressures have changed for motor positions 43 600 and 46 000.

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Erklärung:

Ich versichere, dass ich diese Arbeit selbstständig verfasst habe und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt habe.

Heidelberg, den 12.04.22

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